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MORPHOLOGICAL AND GENOMIC CHARACTERIZATION OF INDIGENOUS
BREED OF GOATS (*Capra hircus*) IN KANO STATE USING MICROSATELLITE
MARKERS

BY

ISA TAPEN ISA
(SPS/18/MAS/00004)
B. Agric Tech, ATBU

A DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO THE SCHOOL OF POSTGRADUATE
STUDIES, BAYERO UNIVERSITY KANO, IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENT FOR THE AWARD OF THE DEGREE OF MASTER OF
SCIENCE IN ANIMAL SCIENCE (ANIMAL GENETICS AND BREEDING).

AUGUST, 2023

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this work is the product of my research efforts undertaken under the supervision of Dr. I. O. Suleiman and that the work has not been presented anywhere for the award of a degree or certificate. All sources have been duly acknowledged.

Isa Tapen Isa
SPS/18/MAS/00004

Date

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the research work for this dissertation and the subsequent write-up by Isa Tapen Isa (SPS/18/MAS/00004) was carried out under our supervision.

Dr. I. O Suleiman
Supervisor

Date

Dr. S.K Inusa
Head of Department

Date

APPROVAL PAGE

This dissertation has been examined and approved for the award of Masters of
Science in Animal Science (Animal Genetics and Breeding)

External Examiner

Sign/ Date

Internal Examiner
Prof M. Baba

Sign/Date

Supervisor
Dr. I.O. Suleiman

Sign/Date

Head of Department
Dr. S.K. Inusa

Sign/Date

SPS Representative
Dr. S. Rufa'i

Sign/Date

DEDICATION

This research work is dedicated to God Almighty for sparing my life throughout the period of this study. I also dedicate this project to my late mother Mrs. Asma'u Kushong, may God grant you Aljanatul Firdausi, Amin.

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted to investigate the morphological and genomic characteristics of indigenous breeds of goats in Kano state using microsatellite markers. Body weight(kg) and fourteen morphometric measurements(cm) such as body length (BL), Head circumference (HC), Tail Length (TL), Hip Height (HH), Neck Length (NL), Ear Length (EL), Horn Length (HL), Wither Height (WH), Canon Length (CL), Chest Depth (CD), Face Length (FL), Gonadal Length (GL), Gonadal Circumference (GC) and Heart Girth (HG) were taken from the three hundred and seventy four adult goats from eight selected locations (Ungogo, Kumbotso, Dala, Kano Municipal, Wudil, Bebeji, Rimin Gado and Tofa) in Kano State. The parameters were used to determine the relationship between the variables. Body weight was measured in kilograms using weight scale and morphometric parameters using measuring tape. Twenty four blood samples were aspirated from the four breeds (Sahel, Kano Brown, Red Sokoto and West Africa dwarf) for laboratory analysis. The body weight and morphometric measurements had significant ($P < 0.01$) difference. The interaction effect on sex and age had significant ($P < 0.01$) difference on the entire morphometric trait measured. Pearson correlation analysis for all the variables measured showed positive and significant relationship. Among the population sampled the genetic similarity ranged from 0.669 – 1.000 while the genetic distance range from 0.066 – 0.402. The population was not genetically pure but heterogeneous with varying degree of genetic similarity and distance. Since there was no inbreeding as shown in the study, none of the population exhibited genetic uniqueness. The result showed the presence of wide morphological and phenotypic variations within and among the indigenous breeds of goat. The rich adaptable morphological traits could be exploited for future goat breeds improvement programme. It is recommended that morphometric and genetic characteristics should be used to generate reliable information for goat discrimination due to their morphological and genomic differences.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND INFORMATION

Domestic animals have played a key role in human history. The goat is the earliest domestic animal and probably the first ruminant livestock, after the wolf was domesticated (Hole, 1996; Uerpmann, 1996). There are two reasons for this: firstly, the wild goat was reported to be present in the regions of southwest Asia during the time when agriculture was developing. Secondly, the goat is an extremely hardy animal, hence, could have withstood the rigours of being reduced to the state of domestication better than other ruminants. Goats were domesticated at first for meat. However, as a dairy animal, the goat is regarded as the oldest, even older than cattle (Devendra & Burns, 1983).

Goat (*Capra hircus*) farming is a vital part of the national economy in many countries and plays a significant role in the socio-cultural life of the rural community and in preserving marginal areas (Willi, Buskirk & Hoffmann, 2006) especially in West Africa. Goats constitute the largest group of small ruminant livestock in Nigeria totaling about 76 million and also constituting 7.6 percent of the World's goat population (FAO, 2021). Surveys have shown that up to 85 percent of rural households, poor farmers and small-time business people of all age groups and sexes keep goat (Kotze, Swart, Grobber & Nemaamgani, 2004).

Breeds are a homogenous, sub specific group of domestic livestock with definable and identifiable external characteristics that enable it to be classified, using visual appraisal, from other similarly defined group within the same species (FAO, 2000). There are four breeds of goat in Nigeria namely; Red Sokoto, Sahel, West African dwarf and Kano brown. Red Sokoto are well known for their usefulness in the

tanning industries, the Sahel goat is an extant meat and milk production in Nigeria, West African Dwarf are used almost exclusively for meat and skin production and Kano brown are well known for meat production.

The benefits derived from this important of livestock species remain unchanged. The output is low compared to improved breeds (exotic breed). Therefore, genetic resource of this important species need to be exploited. First step involve in any animal genetic improvement programme s to describe the important of morphometric traits. Variation in body size is one of the criteria used in classifying the breed of good morphometric characteristics are also essential in breed identification and classification which aid in appropriate breeding design, feeding and health management (Gizaw *et al.*, 2007).

The conservation of farm animal genetic resources is important for coping with future breeding needs and for facilitating the sustainable use of marginal areas. It is often said that variation in genes is necessary to allow organisms to adapt to ever-changing environments (Orr & Unckless, 2014). However, it is actually the variation in alleles that is critical. According to Dubey (2009), variation in alleles or markers can be detected at three different levels: morphological or phenotypic which corresponds to quantitative traits scored visually; biochemical due to differences in proteins; and molecular (a sequence among which the differences can be detected and monitored in the subsequent generations). Measurement of genetic diversity in goats has been imprecise because earlier studies were based on morphological and biochemical markers. Because of the influence of both natural and artificial selection on phenotypic traits as well as great influence of environment on both of these types of markers, it is unlikely that observations based on the study of differences between breeds would produce reliable results. Molecular markers such as microsatellite

markers are more accurate because of their dense distribution in the genome, great variation, co-dominant inheritance and easy genotyping at DNA level. Microsatellites are repeats of simple sequences, the commonest being dinucleotide repeats which are abundant in genomes of all higher organisms, including livestock (Weber & May, 1989). Polymorphism of microsatellites takes the form of variation in the number of repeats at any given locus and is generally revealed as fragment length variation in the products of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification of genomic DNA using primers flanking the chosen repeat sequence and specific for a given locus (Kemp & Teal, 1991).

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Goats in the highlands are widely distributed in the mixed crop-livestock production systems with very small flock size as a means of cash earnings and meat. Although there are severe environmental constraints to increase goat productivity, there is considerable potential for improved goat production in the country, where goat milk, meat, and skin are a valued commodities (Tesfaye, 2004).

Indigenous breeds have not been characterized in many African countries and it would be tragic to lose these unique genetic resources that are the result of centuries of human and natural selection (Leak, Faye & Geerts, 2002). The rate of erosion of indigenous animal genetic resources therefore threatens the prospect of improving the livelihood of present and future human generations. Developing countries host a vast majority of indigenous farm animal genetic resources (over 90 percent) that unfortunately are not being improved to respond to global food security needs (FAO, 1999). FAO estimates that 30 percent of livestock breeds are at risk of extinction and about six breeds are lost per month. Moreover, more than half of these breeds are found in developing countries (FAO, 2000). However, sustainable conservation and

utilization of these indigenous goat resources cannot begin until their genetic diversity is understood and quantified.

Genetic variation between and within breed is described as diversity and it is a valuable asset as the adaptability of a population, depends on it (Woolliams, Berg, Maki-Tanila, Meuwissen & Fimland, 2005). It is well known that species can face great environmental changes over time, such as in climate, pollution and disease; and genetic diversity is required for populations to adapt to these changes (Frankham, Ballou & Briscoe, 2002). If genetic diversity is very low, none of the individuals in the population may have the characteristics needed to cope with the new environmental conditions or challenge. Such a population could be suddenly wiped out. Also, low genetic diversity increases the vulnerability of populations to catastrophic events such as disease outbreaks. Loss of genetic diversity is often associated with inbreeding, selection, gene flow and migration (Frankham *et al.*, 2002; Willi *et al.*, 2006). Although Nigerian goat is not at risk of extinction, when considering the downward trend, this breed may face the risk of genetic erosion due to natural disasters and epidemic diseases (Bahmani, Tahmoorespour & Aslaminiejad, 2011).

The investigation of genetic diversity at the molecular level has been proposed as a valuable complement to the evaluation of the genetic, phenotypes and production systems, and sometimes as a proxy for phenotypic diversity of local breeds (Murital *et al.*, 2015). This has expanded our insight into breed history, in order to guide breed development, utilization and conservation decisions. Furthermore, as the demand for certified products such as meat and milk is increasing, the focus is now on local indigenous breeds. Consequently, indigenous populations will be at a higher risk of genetic erosion due to selection pressure, indiscriminate mating and lack of

characterization, unless adequate steps are taken to characterize and conserve their genetic diversity (Suleiman, 2017). A detail genetic diversity study on the similarity between and within breeds of local goat populations is therefore imperative in quantifying the structure of genetic diversity, utilization strategies and developing effective management plans for the optimization of conservation and improvement of the genetic resources.

1.3 JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

For effective utilization of goat genetic resources, it is necessary to genetically characterize different populations. Such characterization would provide a database with information on which of the populations represent homogeneous breeds and which are genetically distinct. This characterization, contributes to the understanding of the evolutionary history of goats as well as future conservation and management of goat genetic resources (Muema, Wakhungu, Hanotte, & Jianlin, 2009; Okpeku, *et al.*, 2011a)

Therefore, given the importance of these breeds and the need to identify genetic variability in the Nigeria goat population, it is necessary to assess the genetic diversity within these breeds. In fact, genetic diversity is fundamental for long-term survival of populations providing the raw material for adaptation and evolution, especially when environmental conditions have changed (Eriksson, Namkoong & Roberds, 1993). Thus, the genetic characterization of native breeds is the first step for their conservation. The use of highly variable molecular genetic markers, such as microsatellites is one of the most powerful tools to study genetic diversity because of its high polymorphic degree, random distribution across genome and neutrality with respect to selection (Kemp *et al.*, 1995).

The availability of new molecular techniques for large scale genetic characterization is providing unique opportunities to tackle the above issues. These techniques are able to reveal genetic distances between populations allowing a better understanding of how these populations evolved. In view of the above, it would be ideal to characterize at the molecular level the Nigerian goats in order to determine their genetic diversity and describe the relationship among the different populations. The information provided will allow formulation of conservation programs, maximizing diversity conserved and it may guide breeding improvement activities for meat and milk production (Meghen, MacHugh & Bradley, 1994).

The primary measure should be to determine the magnitude of genetic differentiation and relationship among the populations. One way of doing this is to determine genetic distances between pairs of breeds/populations. The computation of genetic distances requires estimation of allele frequency data using either protein markers or DNA markers. However, techniques for the determination of polymorphism of protein products lack the power to resolve the differences between closely related breeds since a great deal of genetic variation remains undetected by these methods (Meghen *et al.*, 1994; Dowling, Moritz, Palmer & Rieseberg, 1996).

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this study was to morphologically and genetically characterize the indigenous goat breeds using specific microsatellite markers.

The specific objectives were;

1. To examine the morphometric characters among the breeds of goat in Kano State.
2. To determine the influence of location, breed, age and sex on morphometric attributes of goat in the study area.

3. To evaluate existing genetic variation within and among goat populations in Kano State.
4. To determine the genetic distance and similarity or relatedness of the goat population in Kano State.
5. To determine relationship between the variables from the studied goat population.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 THE GOAT (*Capra hircus*)

The goat is a member of the Bovidae family and is closely related to the sheep: both are in the goat-antelope sub-family caprinae. There are over three hundred distinct breeds of goat. Goats are one of the oldest domesticated species. Goats have been used for their milk, meat, hair and skin over much of the world. In the twentieth century, they also gained popularity as pets (Udeh, 2015).

Goat is one of the most populated ruminants in Nigeria (Yashim, Adukepe, Abdu, Jokthan & Kabir, 2008). *Capra hircus* is sexually dimorphic, males have beards, horns, a rank odour, and are generally larger than the females. The odour stems from sex glands; the horns are hallowing, and grow either scimitar or corkscrew. The hair is generally straight; however some breeds have wool, under coat colour varies and can be black, white, red and brown. Colour patterns include solid colour, spotted, striped, blended shades and facial stripes. The nose can be either straight or convex. European breeds have erect ears while India breeds do not. The Lamancha breed has no external ear. The tail is short and curved upwards. (Haenlein, 1992).

Female goats are referred to as nannies or does, intact males as bucks or billies; their offspring as kids. Castrated male is called wethers. Goat meat from younger animals is called kid or cabrito, and from older animals is called chevon (Udeh, 2015). Humans usually control the breeding behaviour of domesticated *C. hircus*. Under human control *C. hircus* follows a polygynous reproductive system. In nature, feral groups follow this same pattern. In captivity, certain males may be chosen by humans to sire the young of several females. The females are then

inseminated either directly by those males or by artificial insemination. Left to their own devices, male goats compete for rank, and the highest ranking males have access to mate with the females. Sex glands are used to produce pheromones which attract the females. Males fight by butting heads until one competitor surrenders (Vaughan, Ryan & Nicholas, 2000).

2.2 HISTORY OF GOATS

The goat (*Capra hircus*) is thought to have been the first animal to be domesticated for economic purposes around 9000-10000 BC. It was brought by migrant's pastoralist from Asia to Africa (Devendra & Mcleroy, 1988). There is hardly a climatic zone without goats. Immediately after domestication, physical differentiation into breeds and types began. Early physical changes affected the ears, horns, colour and hair type. These changes arose from natural mutation and from selection by goat keepers within the environment in which goats were reared, usually in relative isolation. Early goat keepers must have selected from the production characteristics which were appropriate to their needs. New blood probably entered goat populations when people migrated for economic reasons or in times of conflict. There is a huge range of size, colour, and hair type among modern breeds of goats (Peacock, 1996).

2.3 THE POTENTIALS OF SMALL RUMINANT PRODUCTION IN NIGERIA

Small ruminant animals include goats (*Capra hircus*) and sheep (*Ovis aries*). These animals are highly priced as they provide household meat for consumers and skin for local leather industry. Goats have been reported by Ozung, Nsa, Ebegbulum and Ubu (2011) to contribute 16.0% and sheep 5.0% of total domestically produced meat in Nigeria, which has been estimated at 813,000 tonnes per annum. Sheep and goat skins have been estimated at 7,500 tonnes and 20,400 tonnes per annum (Ozung

et al., 2011). Milk from sheep and goats has been accepted in most developed countries as an alternative to cow milk and their contribution stands at 46% of the world total production of 7.3 million tonnes for sheep and 40% of the total world production of 7.2 million tonnes for goats in both the tropics and subtropics. (Ozung *et al.*, 2011). Sheep and goats play a significant role in the food chain and overall livelihoods of rural households, where they are largely the property of women and their children (Lebbie, 2004). According to Adu, Aina and Okeleye (1996) small ruminants in southern Nigeria are integral component of the household, where they contribute to the cultural, food and socioeconomic life of the people. While Upton (1984) stated that the potential returns from sheep and goat keeping under the traditional management system are high. In south-west Nigeria, goats are used for customary rites in addition to meat production and religious purpose (Odeyinka & Ajayi, 2004). It has been documented that sheep and goats are the principal domesticated small ruminants in terms of total numbers and production of food and fibre production (Winrock, 1983). This attribute may partly be due to their lower feed requirements compared to cattle, because of their body size (Okunlola, Amuda & Ayanwanidi, 2010). This however, allows for easy integration of small ruminants into different farming systems (Hirpa & Abebe, 2008). Traditionally, sheep and goats have served as means of ready cash and a reserve against economic and agricultural production hardship (Hamito, 2008). In temperate zones, goats are kept often as supplementary animals by small holders, while commercially, cows or buffaloes are kept for milk, cheese and meat; and sheep for wool and meat production (NDD, 2004). Okunlola *et al.* (2010) reported a similar trend in Tropical Africa where a majority of small ruminant is owned by individuals or families in rural areas and the number per group is small.

2.4 INDIGENOUS BREEDS OF GOATS

Several authors, (Devendra, 1985; Ademosun, 1985; Egwu, Onyeyilo, Chibuzo & Ameh, 1995) reported on the ecology, morphology, and characteristics of 3 distinct breeds of goats in Nigeria, these include the Red Sokoto goat (Maradi), West African long legged (Sahel, Arab, Maure), and West African dwarf (Cameroon Dwarf, Nigeria Dwarf, Kirdi, and Futa Djalon). Many other “transitional types” perhaps crosses known as Borno white, Borno red, Kano brown and Maiduguri brown named according to their areas of origin are also encountered (Egwu *et al.*, 1995).

2.4.1 Sahelian Goat

The “West African long legged, “Sahel” Fulani”, the desert or Sahalian goat is found along the northern border of Nigeria, particularly Borno State, where it is often known as “Balami, although this name has not been adopted as it would lead to confusion with the better known sheep breed Balami. Mason (1988) uses “Sahel, which seems appropriate, as this breed is distributed from Senegal to Sudan. This breed has thin appearance, narrow body and shallow chest. Both sexes are horned, about 70% with wattle, pendulous or semi-pendulous ears, the coat is white or dapple. Height at withers range between 65-85cm, while the chest girth is 70 – 85cm. The first kidding occurs usually at about 18 months, bearing mostly (70%) one or two kids, with lactation persisting to 5-6 months. it is kept primarily for meat (Devendra & Burns, 1983; Mason, 1996).

2.4.2 Maradi (Red Sokoto) Goat

According to Devendra & Burns (1983) the Red Sokoto goat is one of the few well defined breeds in Africa. The Red Sokoto is also known as maradi goat. The Red Sokoto is the predominant goat and accounts for about 70% of Nigeria’s total goat population which has been estimated at 34.4 million (Ademosun, 1993; Osuhor,

Alawa & Lufadeju, 1998). It is commonly found among the agro-pastoralists mainly within the sub-humid and semi-arid zones of the country (Akpa, Asiribo, Oni & Alawa, 2001a). Over 90% of Red Sokoto goats are managed by the pastoral Fulani (Taiwo, Buvanendran & Adu, 2005). The Red Sokoto goat was the source of 'Morocco leather' known in Europe from the medieval period onwards. The skin of the Red Sokoto is reputed to be of high quality; therefore it is used in the leather industry locally and internationally for fine leather (Akpa, Duru & Amos, 1998) and it is a large, fast growing and early maturing meat producing breed (Upton, 1987; Ngere, 1983) and can be used in improving the meat potentials of the West Africa Dwarf goats. The vast majority of this breed possess a dark brown coat, although very few may possess other coat colours as black, brown or white as a result of cross breeding. Their legs are notably shorter than the Sahel breed and they have short horizontal ears and shorter horns which goes vertically backward. Their height at wither is about 65cm and they have an average weight of 25kg. Both sexes are horned and are adapted to arid zones where meat and skin production are their ultimate uses (Egwu *et al.*, 1995).

2.4.3 West African Dwarf Goat (WAD)

The West Africa Dwarf goat is found in West and Central Africa; they are indigenous to the forest and derived savannah and are well adapted to the humid zones (Egwu *et al.*, 1995). Their height at withers is about 40-50cm and 24.5kg in weight. New born kids average around 1.2kg at birth. Growth rate and milk yield are very low, but twin and triplet births are common and they breed at all times of the year. They are used almost exclusively for meat and skin production. The breed most useful peculiarities are its adaptation to the humid tropical environment and resistance to *trypanosomiasis* (Agyemang, Rawling, Clifford, Bojang & Tamba, 1991).

The West Africa Dwarf goats are widely distributed across the rainforest belt of southern Nigeria. They are short-legged and small bodied animals. They also present variable coat colours, ranging from black, brown, gray, pied, red and white, and sometimes combinations of these in a variety of patterns (Odubote, 1994; Mourad, Gbanamou & Balde, 2000; Ozoje & Mgbere, 2002).

2.4.4 Kano Brown Goat

In the statement made by Adu, Buvanendran and Lakpini (1979) say the Kano Brown goat of Nigeria is often grouped together with Red Sokoto and the Maradi goat from Niger. However, since 2005 the Kano Brown is now considered as a separate ecotype of the Sahelian Goat and is treated as a genetic resource separate from other breeds (Evans, 2012). The Kano Brown is most typically raised by the Hausa people of Kano state of Nigeria and by far the commonest meat breed in the country. Kano state is a semi-arid area with single annual rainfall season 4 – 6 months duration (the rainy season). The breed is of extreme economic importance as it provides the majority of goat meat in Nigeria and it is transported country-wide. The goats are often used as currency and local governments have even used them as payment to families to persuade them to keep girls in education.

The Kano Brown goat is classified as medium-sized animal and is about the same size as the Red Sokoto (from which they descended) but are bulkier and less skinny in appearance, as befits a goat bred for its meat. They are of relatively short size (and may have been crossed with the Nigerian Dwarf Goat). A typical female stands 54 – 65cm tall at the Wither, and the male is slightly taller, measuring some 60 – 65cm tall. Evans (2012) says the goats are characterized by their fine heads and prominent foreheads. The mucous membranes and mouth are black. They have short bodies and proportionally long and flexible necks (which help them to browse). The

ears are short, of medium width and are usually carried horizontally. The males have long beards of profuse hair and the whole head can be hairy. The males also have a mane of hair that extends to the shoulders. Both male and female have short horns. The coats are short and glossy, and range in colour from ruddy brown to chestnut. Tail hairs are typically black. The males are typically darker than the females and may have a black stripe along the back. The udder is full and rounded with well-spaced teats. It is much less divided than the udder of other Nigerian goat breeds. Average weight is 60 – 80kg and lifespan ranges from 10 – 15 years

2.5 MORPHOLOGICAL TRAITS OF GOATS AND FACTORS AFFECTING THEM

Oseni, Sonaiya, Omitogun, Ajayi and Muritala (2006) reported that morphometric measurements are among the data needed in characterization and establishment of breed standards in West Africa Dwarf goat production. As with the presence of horns, beard is a character included by an autosomal sex-dependant gene, it is dominant in males and recessive in females. According to Lauvergne, Renieri and Andiol (1987) and Rodero, De La Haba, Rodero and Aterrera (1996) it is determined by the Br locus, the Brb allele being bearded and the BrA being wild. In the Andalusian white breed, there was a locus with two alleles that determined the colour: Wb for the white coat and Wk for the cream coat, the latter being dominant (Rodero *et al.*, 1996). Thiruvankaden, Pannerselvan and Kandasanny (2000) reported that the hooves and dewclaws of Salem goats are grey in colour. Devendra and Burns (1983) discovered that in Katiang breed of goats, the beards are invariably found in males but is less frequent in the females and in Criollo goats, beards are common in males but not in females. Osuhor *et al.* (1998) described Red Sokoto goats as having a well-defined uniform dark brown colour.

2.5.1 Body Weight

Weight has been the pivot on which animal production thrives. The knowledge on weight assessment is very necessary because as far as all animal production management is concerned, weight assessment remains the backbone on which it is hinged. The knowledge of body weight of goats is important for a number of reasons; it is related to feeding and health care (Thiruvankaden, 2005). Body measurements had been used to predict body weight by several authors in many breeds of goats; Sahel goats of Nigeria (Mohammed & Amin, 1997), Red Sokoto goats (Hassan & Ciroma, 1992; Akpa *et al.*, 1998), West Africa Dwarf goat (Mayaka, Tchoumbove, Manjeli & Tegua, 1995) and kano brown goats (Slipper, Letty & de Villers, 2000).

Body measurement is important for the prediction of live weight, carcass weight and determination of certain body conformation traits that can be taken into consideration in selecting animals for genetic improvement (Akpa, Galadima & Malau-Aduli, 2006). Otoikhian, Otoikhian, Akporhvarho, Oyefia and Isidahomen (2008) showed that there is a positive correlation between increase in body parameters measured with weight gain. This means that animals at different age groups have differences in measurement of body parts like the distance between the eye length, ear width, body weight and tail length (Osinowo & Abubakar 1989; Otoikhian, Imasuen & Orheruata, 2006). Animal live weight is an important feature but are seldom measured in rural areas due to lack of dependable accurate scale (Mayaka *et al.*, 1995). Scales are not readily available in most rural African farming communities (Mani, Abdullahi & von Kanfinann 1991, Nesamvuni, Malaudzi, Ramanyimi & Taylor, 2000).

However quantitative measures for animal conformation are desirable as it will enable reliable genetic parameters for these traits to be estimated and permit their

inclusion in breeding programme (Ibe, 1989). Lawrence and Fowler (1998) recorded that live weight is probably the most widely used technique both in practice and in experimental work, in determining the growth rate in animals and in predicting their likely body composition and therefore the rate at which various tissues grow. Indeed the consensus view from a great deal of research work (Alphonsus, 2008) showed that live weight is the most important single predictor for many carcass traits and is the variable that is most important to hold constant in prediction equation which include other variables. This is especially true for body weight which is a good parameter for meat characteristics as larger sized animals produce more meat (Abegaz & Awgichew, 2009). Ngere, Adu and Okubanjo (1984) and Osuhor, Alawa and Akpa (2002) reported heavier weights for adult bucks compared with does while Ojedapo *et al.*, (2007) reported heavier body weight for does in West African Dwarf goats. Hassan and Ciroma (1990) however reported body lengths ranging from 79 – 97cm for Red Sokoto goats aged 1 – 5 years. Otoikhian *et al.* (2008) recorded that up to 74.4% of body weight can be assessed without having to weigh the goat. Studies have also shown that there are high and significant correlations between height at withers, heart girth and body weight at 1-2years of age suggesting that either of these variables or their combination could provide a good estimate for predicting live weight in Red Sokoto goat at an early age (Hassan & Ciroma, 1990).

2.5.2 Heart Girth (HG)

Heart girth measurement represents the circumference of the chest. Ojedapo *et al.*, (2007) reported a significant ($r = 0.934$) and high correlation coefficient between body weight and heart girth. High correlation between body weight and heart girth has also been reported by Ibiwoye and Oyatogun (1987) in Red Sokoto goats.

Akpa *et al.* (1998) reported mean values of chest girth of Red Sokoto goats at 1 – 6, 7 – 12, 13 – 18, 19 – 24, and 25 – 30 months to be 44.6 ± 2.18 , 57.7 ± 1.86 , 60.1 ± 0.92 , 70.9 ± 1.4 and 70.7 ± 1.60 cm respectively. Thiruvankaden (2005) found that the mean values of heart girth recorded in Kanni Adu kids at 0 – 3, 3 – 6, 6 – 9 and 9 – 12 months were 39.9 ± 0.45 , 51.8 ± 0.51 , 55.5 ± 0.67 and 58.2 ± 0.65 cm respectively. He suggested that the higher association of body weight with chest girth was possible due to relatively larger contribution in body weight by chest girth (consisting of bones, viscera and muscles). Mohammad *et al.*, (2006) reported a mean heart girth in males at 4 – 12, 13 – 18, 19 – 24 and 25 – 36 months as 59.10 ± 0.86 , 66.0 ± 3.19 , 70.29 ± 1.19 , 79.63 ± 0.96 cm while that of females in the same age groups were reported to be 57.60 ± 0.95 , 61.29 ± 1.27 , 64.00 ± 430.68 and 70.15 ± 1.80 cm, respectively in Beetal goats. Hassan and Ciroma (1992) recorded values of heart girth of Red Sokoto goats at 1 – 2, 3 – 4 and 5 years of age to be 61.78 ± 0.73 , 67.36 ± 0.51 and 75.77 ± 0.86 cm respectively.

2.5.3 Height at Withers (HAW)

Height at withers is measured as the distance between the most dorsal point of the withers and the ground level. Thiruvankaden (2005) reported a high correlation between height at withers and body weight in males of 6- 9 months and 9 – 12 months and in females of 0 – 3 months. The author further reported overall mean for height at withers (cm) of Kanni Adu kids at 0-3, 3-6, 6-9 and 9-12 months for males to be 46.7 ± 0.69 , 58.1 ± 1.23 , 64.6 ± 1.04 and 66.2 ± 2.81 respectively. Those of the females were 45.3 ± 0.63 , 58.8 ± 0.64 , 59.7 ± 6.31 and 65.5 ± 0.95 respectively. Akpa *et al.*, (1998) recorded overall mean values of height at withers of Red Sokoto goats at 1 – 6, 7 – 12, 13 – 18, 19 – 24, 25 – 30 and 31 – 36 months to be 38.1 ± 2.09 cm, 47.5 ± 3.26 , 53.3 ± 1.49 , 53.5 ± 1.87 , 64.1 ± 0.83 , 64.1 ± 0.83 cm for males respectively and

39.7 ± 3.29, 51.0 ± 0.89, 52.8 ± 1.37, 52.9 ± 1.25, 59.7 ± 1.41 and 59.8 ± 1.28cm for females respectively. They further reported that sex significantly influenced body weight, body length, height at wither and heart girth. Hassan and Ciroma (1992) reported overall mean values for height at withers of Red Sokoto goats for different age groups of 1 - 2 years, 3 -4 years and 5 years to be 54.44 ± 0.72cm, 61.07 ± 0.49cm and 65.94 ± 0.97cm for females respectively. Eugena (2010) reported that the high positive correlation values between body weight, height at withers and heart girth indicates that as live body weight increase, the linear body measurements will also increase. Adewumi, Chineke, Alokun and Oleadipupo (2006) stated that body weight and linear measurements could be selected for at the same time. Attah and El Khidir (2004) reported from their study that measurements such as chest girth, height at withers were at one stage or the other found to be highly correlated with body weight and gave a value of about 49cm for males and 47cm for females for height at withers.

2.5.4 Body Length (BLT)

Body length refers to the distance from the external occipital protuberance to the base of the tail. Mohammad *et al.*, (2006) recorded body length of males to be 59.60 ± 0.74, 64.38 ± 1.39, 69.42 ± 0.29, 78.15 ± 0.60cm while that of females were found to be 58.70 ± 0.84, 60.14 ± 0.50, 62.16 ± 0.60, 69.31 ± 1.85cm in goats aged between 4 - 12, 13 - 19, 19 - 24, and 25 - 36 months respectively. They further concluded that body weight was correlated with body length (0.49, 0.12, 0.70 and 0.78) in Beetal goats. Ojedapo *et al.*, (2007) and Akpa, Jokthan, Ogunleye and Lakpini (2004) reported a high and positive correlation between body length and weight in West Africa Dwarf and Red Sokoto goats respectively. According to Akpa *et al.*, (1998) the mean body length of Red Sokoto goats for age group 1 - 6, 7 - 12,

13 – 18, 19– 24 and 25 – 30 months of age to be 36.7 ± 2.36 , 44.5 ± 0.50 , 51.0 ± 0.99 , 55.7 ± 2.09 and 63.3 ± 2.20 respectively in males, while the females had 39.7 ± 3.29 , 50.8 ± 0.83 , 53.7 ± 1.43 , 53.8 ± 1.48 , 61.5 ± 1.00 , and 62.1 ± 0.97 respectively. Thiruvankaden (2005) recorded mean values of body length (cm) in Kanni Adu kid at 0-3, 3-6, 6-9 and 9-12 months to be 39.8 ± 0.44 , 51.1 ± 0.29 , 54.1 ± 0.28 and 57.2 ± 0.44 cm respectively. Ibe and Nwakalor (1987) reported that the high correlation between each linear body measurement and body weights is not surprising, since the latter is a measure of overall body growth which itself is the sum total of increases in size of different structural body component. Orheruata, Ikhatua and Omisope (1997) reported that the mean value for male and female Ndama cattle linear body measurements increased with age in a similar manner from birth to 30 months of age, but with the highest increase occurring during pre-weaning period, while the least increase was between 24 and 30 month post weaning. Hassan and Ciroma (1992) reported mean body length of Red Sokoto goats at 1 – 2, 3 – 4 and 5 years as 79.15 ± 0.57 , 85.43 ± 0.91 and 96.44 ± 1.41 cm respectively.

2.5.5 Factors Affecting Morphological Traits.

Age

Fajemilehin and Salako (2008) reported that age strongly influenced body weight and body linear traits in West African Dwarf goats, as there were consistent increase in all the traits studied as the animals aged. This scenario was not surprising since the size and shape of the animal is expected to increase as the animal is growing with age. This was in consonance with the report of Orheruata and Olutogun (1994) in cattle. Ojedapo *et al;* (2007) reported that age affected the least square means of body weight and some linear body measurements and the value obtained for all the measurements increased as the animals advanced in age. The slow growth that

occurred in goats between 1½ - 2 years was not an indication that goat had attained maturity. It could be explained that in this period (1½ - 2years) in goats, energy is centered towards weight gain than elongation of body parts. Thus, by measurement of some of the body parameters, the age of goats can be assessed and the timing for different management practices can be pegged accurately to bring goats to a good and desired weight at maturity (Imasuen & Otoikhian, 2004).

Sex of kids

Studies have shown that sex does not have any influence on weight gain of goats (Otoikhian *et al.*, 2006; Imasuen & Otoikhian, 2004). Ozoje and Herbert (1997) also observed that sex did not significantly affect body length, heart girth, leg length, and shoulder width either at birth or at any other age up to when the kids are weaned in West Africa Dwarf and Red Sokoto goats. On the contrary, Akpa *et al.*, (1998) reported that sex significantly influenced body weight, body length, height at withers and heart girth for different age groups in Red Sokoto goats with males recording higher values. Fajemilehin and Salako (2008) reported in their study that more female animals than males were available for screening and so observed that sex had an influence on body weight and body linear measurements. Giving the impression that sex is an important source of variation for body weight and body linear measurements at the two age groups (young and adult) of animals available for measurement. They also observed that the females were heavier than males at these ages and linear measurements were superior because female goats grew faster than the bucks at early stage. This sex influenced differences in body weight and linear measurements was partly attributed to hormonal effect, that is, non-release of androgen (which is known to have growth and weight stimulating effects) in male animals until the testes are well developed (Frandsen & Elmer, 1981). Fajemilehin and Salako (2008) reported

that male animals from only two age groups were available for screening and that this was because farmers will want to keep female goats in preference to males to minimize cost of feeding and to increase production efficiency. They also observed that most of the males were preferably castrated and fattened for sale as meat and as source of income to the owners.

Further report (Fajemilehin & Salako, 2008; Ifut, Essien & Udoh, 1991) showed that sex significantly influenced body weight and body conformation in West Africa Dwarf goats. Akpa *et al.* (1998) concluded that both sex and strains significantly influenced body weight and linear traits. Whenzhong, Zhang and Zhong-Xiao (2005) reported that sex was a major factor influencing body weight and growth rate. They observed that females were larger than males for all body sizes except withers height. Al-Shorepy, Alhadrami and Abdulwahab (2002) found that sex effect was significant for all traits. Male kids were heavier and grow faster than female kids. A weight difference of 0.23kg (9.0%) at birth increased to 1.55kg (13.3%) at weaning. Sex difference increased with growth rate, indicating that male kids were more responsive to improvement in environment.

Heart girth

According to Thiruvankaden (2005) reported that the heart girth is also known as chest girth or chest circumference. It is measured as the circumference of the body at a point immediately behind the forelimbs, perpendicular to the body axis. Heart girth measurement is considered because of its high heritability and association with body weight (Alade, Abdul-Kareem & Asheik, 2008). According to Isaac and Ibrahim (2006) chest girth showed the highest correlation for both sexes. Their report was an indication that chest girth succeeded in estimating body weight more than any of the other linear body measurement. Giving the impression that heart

girth would give the best estimate for predicting live weight of Red Sokoto goats at 1-2 years of age. Isaac and Ibrahim (2006) concluded that although chest girth is the most highly correlated trait to body weight, combining it with other linear body measurement (height at withers and body length in a stepwise multiple regression) will produce the best prediction equation for body weight. Thiruvankaden (2005) suggested that the higher association of body weight with chest girth was possible due to relatively larger contribution in body weight by chest girth (consisting of bones, muscles and viscera).

Breed

Breed effect had been reported by Bilaspuri and Singh (1992) and could be attributed to body weight differences (Alade *et al.*, 2008). Moruppa and Ngere (1987) reported breed differences in regression coefficients of body weight on height at withers, heart girth, upper and lower fore limbs and hind limbs in Borno white and Red Sokoto goats, with the former maintaining higher values. Body weight and linear body measurements were found to be higher in Borno white when compared with Red Sokoto and West African Dwarf goats. Ozoje and Herbert (1997) revealed that Red Sokoto goat was superior to the West Africa Dwarf goat at maturity in terms of weight and body measurements.

Season of breeding

Ozoje and Herbert (1997) found that season of breeding significantly affected body length, heart girth and leg length at birth. At 90 and 150 days, seasonal effect was significant for shoulder width and non-significant on heart girth and body length. However, kids born in the dry season (October to April) had superior body length, shoulder width and leg length at birth. Fasae, Cheneke and Alokun (2005) reported in the study of Yankasa ewes in the humid zone of Nigeria, that season had significant

effect on live body weight, chest girth, trunk length and height at withers were significantly higher in the rainy season than in the dry season.

Type of birth

The type of birth such as single, twins or triplets born is known to have some influence on birth weight, body weight, and linear body measurements. Ozoje and Herbert (1997) in their research discovered that type of birth had no significant effect on all measurements; body length, heart girth, leg length and shoulder width. Amoa, Gelaye, Guthrice and Rexroad (1996) reported a decrease in birth weight as the litter size increased. Whenzhong *et al.* (2005) reported that all body size parameters except body length, chest girth, cannon circumference and height at withers were significantly affected by the type of birth and rearing. The kids born as twins had lower birth weight and slower growth rate when compared with those born as single. Al-Shorepy *et al.*, (2002) found that singles were heavier than twins from birth weight, 30 days weight and weaning weight and grew faster from 30 to 90 days of age.

2.6 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MORPHOLOGICAL AND CONFORMATION TRAITS

According to Oseni and Ajayi (2008) conformation traits that were highly correlated with body weight include body length, body depth, hearth girth, height at withers and height at rump. Akpa *et al.*, (1998) also observed that brown and light brown Red Sokoto goats were predominantly heavier in body weight and had higher height at withers. However, Semakula, Mutetikka, Kugonza and Mpairewe (2010) reported that coat colour had no significant effect on height at withers of small East Africa goat breeds of Uganda. Ozoje and Kadir (2001) also recorded no significant

differences in body measurement taken on West Africa Dwarf sheep when coat type was considered.

2.7 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BODY WEIGHT AND BODY MEASUREMENT

Thiruvankaden (2005) reported that correlation co-efficient between body weight and body measurements were positive and strong. The correlation coefficient for different body weight ranged between 0.560 and 0.968. The chest girth accounted for maximum of 80.4 and 93.6% of body weight. Hamayun *et al.*, (2006) observed high and significant correlation co-efficient between height at withers and heart girth and body weight at 4 to 18 months of age in Beetal goats. Suggesting that either of these variables or their combination would provide a good estimate for predicting live body weight in Beetal goat at an early age. The correlation obtained for the above variables were ($r = 0.638$ and $r = 0.552$). Similar trend was also reported in Red Sokoto goats (Moruppa & Ngere, 1987). Hassan and Ciroma (1992) found that body weight in Red Sokoto goat was correlated with body length, height at withers and heart girth within the age groups of 1 -2 years, 3 – 4 years and 5 years, respectively. Akpa *et al.* (1998) reported that Red Sokoto goat body weight was significantly and positively correlated with body length (0.74, 0.63, 0.60 and 0.65), Height at withers (0.79, 0.60, 0.51, 0.47 and 0.46) and chest girth (0.72, 0.57, 0.76, 0.72 and 0.75), 1 – 6 months, 7 -12 months, 13 – 18 months, 19 – 24 months, and 25 – 36 months respectively. Concluding that based on the magnitude of the correlations, heart girth and body length could be used to estimate body weights in Maradi goat across all ages.

According to Singh, Singh and Mishra (1992) birth weight, body weight and body measurements can be used in selection indices to improve body weight at 3 and 6 months of age. An index that incorporated body weight, body length, height at

withers, and heart girth at 3 months gave the highest expected genetic gain at 3 and 6 months of age.

2.8 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DESCRIPTIVE AND BODY CONFORMATION TRAITS

Ozoje and Kadir (2001) reported that define significantly affected body measurement traits in West Africa Dwarf Sheep, sheep with define had longer body length, height at wither, heart girth, shoulder width, tail length, heart depth, leg length and abdominal circumference. Bratte, Ari and Ikhimioya (1999) reported that the horn development generally increases with age and body size, and the coefficient of determination (R^2) relating average horn length (AHL) to ram age and body weight indicated that 84.13% of the variation in AHL could be attributed to its linear relationship with ram age, while 54.34% of the variation can be attributed to body weight. In Salem goats, the body measurements increased progressively as the age advanced (Thiruvnkaden *et al.*, 2000).

2.9 GENETIC PARAMETER ESTIMATES AND IMPROVEMENT STRATEGIES

The genetic makeup of the individual includes additive and non-additive genetic combinations. These combinations interact with the environmental conditions such as climate, nutrition and management and intrinsic factors such as sex, age, physiological status as well as other extrinsic factors (Maternal effect and random environmental factors) to determine the ultimate expression of animal performance (Wattiaux, 2002). The goal of livestock production is to produce quantity and quality products with maximum efficiency. Unbiased heritability and repeatability estimates as well as accurate correlations (genetic and phenotypic) among performance traits in the breeding objective and the selection criteria are required to design selection programme for livestock. (Neopane, 2000).

Estimation of genetic parameters is very important for any genetic improvement program. Heritability estimates for growth traits in goats have been reported to be moderate to high (0.30 – 0.53) (Bosso, Cisse, Vander Waaji, Fall and van Arendonk, 2007; Neopane, 2000). High repeatability estimates (0.70 – 0.89) have been reported for body weight and body measurements in sheep (Tomar, 1979). Studies have also shown that body weight and body measurements are strongly and positively correlated in goats (Akpa *et al.*, 1998; Atta & El-Khidir, 2004; Thiruvenkaden, 2005). Heritability, repeatability and phenotypic correlations of growth traits of Red Sokoto goats were estimated (Iyiola-Tunji *et al.*, 2008). Heritability estimates were 0.99, 0.97, 0.76 and 0.70 for adjusted weaning weight, weaning weight, yearling weight and post weaning daily gain. The repeatability of birth weight, adjusted weaning weight and weaning weight was 0.39, 0.28, and 0.17, respectively.

In the tropics, majority of indigenous small ruminant genetic resources are kept by small holders, making their involvement in improvement and conservation program essential (Kosgey, Baker, Udo & van Arendonk, 2006). So far, breeding improvements targeted at the small holder herds have failed to give desired results due to the movement of breeding does in the herds before the projects were concluded (Akpa, Osuho, Nwani & Lakpini, 2001b). Genetic improvement programs in low input system could be greatly enhanced if they were designated to primarily target farmers (Ahuya, Okeyo, Mwangi- Njuru & Peacock, 2005). Where flock sizes are small, farmers know their animals very well and in many cases can recall the pedigree of the animals (Oliver *et al.*, 2002). In demonstrating such programs, it is preferable to start with a few of the most important traits in a breeding objective rather than a combination of all the traits (Philipson, Rage & Okeyo, 2006). If measurements such

as animal weights are linked to prices in organized marketing system, farmers will quickly realize how useful records are and adopt them (Kosgey & Okeyo, 2007). Adaptability of genotypes to the existing and future environment as well as the need and aspirations of the farmers is paramount for genetic improvement of small ruminants at smallholder level (Baker & Gray, 2004).

2.10 PHENOTYPIC CHARACTERIZATION

According to FAO (2015) the term phenotypic characterization of animal genetic resources generally refers to the process of identifying distinct breed populations and describing their external and performance characteristics within given production environments. The process involves desk work in gathering existing data, as well as field work recording information (descriptions, photos and trait measurements) for sampled animals. The term “production environment”, in this context, refers not only to the “natural” environment (climate, terrain, etc), but also to management practices and the uses to which the animals are put. Broadly defined, it can also be taken to include social and economic factors such as market orientation, marketing opportunities and gender issues. Recording the geographical distribution of breed populations is considered to be an integral part of phenotypic characterization (FAO, 2015). Phenotypic characterization is used to identify and document diversity within and between distinct breeds, based on their observable attributes (FAO, 2012a). Phenotypic characterization, may include information on body biometry, performance, strategies for adaptation, unique testing. Unless we know the accurate physical and biometric characters between and within geographic locations, populations, animal husbandry practices, utility of the particular animal breed which influence these traits their overall improvement cannot be properly designed.

Body shapes measured objectively could improve selection for growth by enabling the breeder to recognize early-maturing and late-maturing animals of different size (Gilbert, Bailey & Shannon 1993). Significant differences in different body measurement traits due to age and sex were reported by many workers in different breeds and species. The guidelines on phenotypic characterization (FAO, 2012b) offer advice on how to conduct a well-targeted and cost-effective phenotypic characterization study and provide an overview of the concepts and approaches that underpin phenotypic characterization. FAO (2012a) also provides practical guidance on planning and implementing of field work, data management and data analysis. Generic data collection formats for phenotypic characterization of major livestock species, as well as a frame work for recording data on breeds' production environments are also included.

2.11 HARDY-WEINBERG EQUILIBRIUM (HWE)

According to Falconer and Mackay (1996), reported that Hardy-Weinberg Equilibrium law states that in a large random mated populations with no selection, migration or mutation, the allelic or gene frequencies and the genotype frequencies remain constant from one generation to the next generation. Thus, a population with constant gene and genotype frequencies is said to be in Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE), Chi-square test is useful for determining whether the allelic frequencies are in HWE or not. Hardy-Weinberg assumption is under the following consideration according to Mariette and Kremer, (1999) are diploid, sexual reproduction, random mating, no selection, no mutation and no migration.

2.12 GENETIC RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN POPULATIONS

2.12.1 Allelic Frequencies and Heterozygosity's in Population Studies

According to Nei, (1972); explain that The Mean Number of Alleles (MNA) detected in each population and the expected heterozygosity's are good indicators of the genetic polymorphism within populations. The MNA is the average number of alleles observed in a population, while the expected heterozygosity's are the proportion of heterozygote expected in a population. Numbers of alleles per locus per population are obtained by direct counting. Generally, the MNA is dependent on the sample size because of the presence of unique alleles that occur in low frequencies in populations and also because the number of observed alleles tend to increase with increases with population size

2.12.2 Genetic Distance between Populations

According to Avis, (1994), Genetic distance is a measurement of genetic relatedness of samples of populations (whereas genetic diversity represents diversity within a population). The estimate is based on the number of allelic substitutions per locus that have occurred during the separate evolution of two populations. This difference measured between two populations provides a good estimate of how divergent they are genetically

Therefore, when the genetic distance is large, the genetic similarity is low and the time they diverged from each other is greater, while when genetic distance is small the genetic similarity is high and the time, they diverged from each other is smaller. Cavalli-Sforza and Edwards (1967) were the first to use gene frequency data to classify populations. They used genetic distance data to construct a phylogenetic tree to infer the history of various human populations. One of the common measures of genetic distance in use today is Nei's standard genetic distance (DS) (Nei, 1972). In

the reports of Okpeku *et al.*, (2011) on the Nigerian goat breeds, genetic distance between Sahel and West African Dwarf was (0.662), Sahel and Red Sokoto (0.444), Red Sokoto and West African Dwarf (0.268).

Adebambo, Williams, Adebambo, Blott and Urquart (2011) reported that the genetic distance between Western African Dwarf goat and Red Sokoto (Maradi) was 0.39. Populations with many similar genes have small genetic distances. This indicates that they are closely related and have a recent common ancestor. Genetic distance is useful for reconstructing the history of populations. For example, evidence from genetic distance suggests that African and Eurasian people diverged about 100,000 years ago (Nei 1972). Genetic distance is also used for understanding the origin of biodiversity. For example, the genetic distances between different breeds of domesticated animals are often investigated in order to determine which breeds should be protected to maintain genetic diversity (Raune, 1999)

2.12.3 F-statistics

This refers to fixation indices, F_{st} and F_{it} which are used to partition genetic variation. Fixation indices are measures of standardized variances in allele frequencies that detect departure from HWE caused by inbreeding, biased outbreeding or population subdivision and drift (Weir & Cockerham, 1984). Weir and Cockerham (1984); the subscript i , s and t refer to individual, subpopulation and total population respectively. The F -statistics is a measure of the difference between the mean heterozygosity among subdivisions in a population and potential frequency of heterozygote, if all members of a population mixed freely and more assertively. F_{is} detects inbreeding in individuals relative to subpopulation (within individuals within populations). This parameter can range from -1 to 1 indicating maximal inbreeding

and outbreeding respectively. A positive F_{is} value indicates inbreeding as the observed heterozygosity is lower than the expected heterozygosity.

F_{st} detects inbreeding in subpopulations relative to the total population, when F_{st} equals zero, it means that subpopulations have identical allele frequency and fixed for different allele. It is always positive and F_{st} is better for population estimates in cases where high level of gene flow is present. If F_{st} is between 0-0.05, it is considered small, 0.05-0.15, moderate and 0.15 and above large. F_{it} can range from -1 to 1, indicating maximal inbreeding and out-breeding respectively Weir and Cockerham, (1984).

2.12.4 Genetic Differentiation of Populations (F_{st})

Donnelly and Townson, (2000) reported the populations of most, if not all species show some levels of genetic structure, which may be due to a variety of non-mutually exclusive agents. Environmental barriers, historical processes and life histories (e.g. mating system) may all, to some extent, shape the genetic structure of populations. The understanding of the genetic differentiation between populations is of interest to population geneticists because it reflects the number of alleles exchanged between populations which influence the genetic composition of individuals within these populations (Balloux and Lugon-Moulin, 2002).

F_{st} measures the effect of population subdivision, which is the reduction in heterozygosity in a subpopulation due to genetic drift. F_{st} is the most inclusive measure of population substructure and is most useful for examining the overall genetic divergence among subpopulations. It is also called co-ancestry coefficient (θ) (Weir and Cockerham, 1984) or 'fixation index' and is defined as correlation of gametes within subpopulations relative to gametes drawn at random from the entire population (Subpopulation within the Total population).

Fst is always positive; it ranges between 0 = panmixis (no subdivision, random mating occurring, no genetic divergence within the population) and 1 = complete isolation (extreme subdivision). Fst values between 0-0.05 indicate negligible (small) genetic differentiation whereas, 0.05-0.15 moderate differentiation, greater than 0.15 means very great genetic differentiation within the population analysed. Fst is usually calculated for different genes, and then averaged across all loci, and all populations. This highly versatile parameter is even used as a genetic distance measure between two populations instead of a fixation index among many populations (Weir 1996; Kalinowski, 2002). Elucidation of genetic variability and genetic relationship among breeds has direct relevance with the issues of sustainable use of domestic animal genetic resources.

In the study conducted by Murital *et al.* (2015) genetic polymorphism was evaluated using 22 microsatellite loci in unrelated samples of Red Kandhari and Deon cattle breeds inhabiting the same geographical area of Marathwada region in Maharashtra state (western India). The study was mainly aimed at assessing the genetic diversity to understand whether the two zebu populations in question are genetically differentiated. A total of 164 alleles were detected with an average of 5.82 and 5.86 alleles per locus (MNA) in Red Kandhari and Deon breeds, respectively. They equally reported that the estimated mean observed (H_o) and expected (H_e) heterozygosity were 0.47 and 0.64 in Red Kandhari vs. 0.57 and 0.69 in Deon cattle, respectively, demonstrating considerable level of genetic variation in both the populations. Mean estimates of F statistics were: F (F_{it}) = 0.315 \pm 0.035, f (F_{is}) = 0.231 \pm 0.031, θ (F_{st}) = 0.110 \pm 0.022, with both the breeds exhibiting significant deficit of heterozygotes (F_{IS} = 0.179 in Deoni; 0.278 in Red Kandhari).

The multilocus F_{st} values implied that 11.0% of the total genetic variation corresponds to breed and were statistically greater than zero for the two populations, suggesting population division. The evaluation of exact test also indicated that allele frequencies across all the loci differed significantly between two zebu breeds, further supporting population differentiation. Different genetic distance measures showed considerable levels of distances between the two cattle breeds (0.318 = Nei's standard DS; 0.250 = Nei's DA; 0.416 = Cavalli-Sforza and Edwards's D_c ; 0.164 = Reynold's, and 2.64 = Delta mu square (d_{micro})². Bayesian statistical approach to assign each individual to the population also supported considerable differentiation between the two cattle breeds, possibly reflecting the limited gene flow between the two Marthwada cattle populations. The existence of cohesive breeding structure of both the breeds was further substantiated by allele-sharing distance measures (DAS) among individual animals. The results of the study thus revealed that the two *Bos indicus* breeds sharing the common breeding tracts are genetically differentiated enough as separate breeds.

2.12.5 Gene Flow between Populations (Nm)

Gene flow is the transfer of alleles from one population to another population through immigration of individuals. (Nassiry, Javanmard & Tohidi, 2009). In population genetics, gene flow is also known as gene migration. Migration into or out of a population may be responsible for a marked change in allele frequencies, immigration may also result in the addition of new genetic variants to the established gene pool of a particular species or population. Gene flow between populations determines the effects of selection and genetic drift; generates new polymorphisms and increases the local effective population size (Balloux and Lugon-Moulin, 2002).

2.12.6 Genetic Diversity

Genetic diversity refers to the variation at the level of individual genes (polymorphism), and provides a mechanism for populations to adapt to their ever-changing environment. The more variation the better the chance that at least some of the individuals will have an allelic variant that is suited for the new environment and will produce offspring with the variant that will in turn reproduce and continue the population into subsequent generations Murital *et al.* (2015). According to Yoseph, (2007) who reported that the Estimation of genetic variability and relationship among different livestock breeds are important for management of genetic resources for their sustainable utilization and conservation. This is more important when the livestock species, like camel, have shown a sharp decline in head count during the last decade.

The authors estimated genetic variability and relationship among four camel breeds of India using 23 microsatellite loci. A total of 252 alleles were observed across all the four populations with mean number of alleles per locus as 8.04, 7.30, 6.39, and 7.43 for Bikaneri, Jaisalmeri, Kutchi, and Mewari breeds, respectively. The mean observed heterozygosity of the four breeds were 0.58, 0.57, 0.56, and 0.60 for Bikaneri, Jaisalmeri, Kutchi, and Mewari breeds, respectively and were lower than expected heterozygosity values. The mean estimates of F statistics were 0.227+/-0.044 (F(it)), 0.157+/-0.038 (F(is)), and 0.082+/-0.019 (F(st)). The values were significantly different from zero for all the three measures and point towards the existence of population structure and moderate differentiation in four camel breeds. The exact test also indicated significant population differentiation. The analysis of molecular variance revealed 12% of the variation attributed to among populations and 88% within populations. Sixty-nine percent of the individuals could be correctly assigned using "leave one out" procedure. All the individuals of Mewari and 42 out of

44 Jaisalmeri were correctly assigned. The existence of strong population structure in Jaisalmeri and Mewari camel was further substantiated by Nei's standard genetic distance as well as interindividual allele sharing distance. Thus, these two breeds owing to selection for specific traits are distinct from other camel breeds. (Nassiry, Javanmard & Tohidi, 2009).

2.13 GOAT GENETIC RESOURCES IN NIGERIAN

Indigenous breeds constitute well over 95 percent of small ruminant populations in Africa (Rege, 1992a). These are well adapted to the environment and the ravages of various kinds such as drought, famine and civil wars that continually plague the continent. Migration to a new habitat and consequently the effect of natural and artificial selection have led to the evolution of breeds and types of goat, which differ in appearance and performance. Around 90 'breeds' of African goats have been recognized using criteria as geographic distributions, ecotypes or communities-tribe ownership (Rege, 1992b). They presumably derive from goats that spread south from Egypt at an early date. Generally, goats of sub-Saharan Africa are divided into three major types following their morphology; the long lop-eared type in north east and southern Africa, the small short-eared type dominant in eastern Africa and the dwarf short-eared type of West Africa. Intermediates morphological types are numerous (Dunham, 2004).

The majority of Nigerian goat population is found in large flocks in the arid and semi-arid lowlands where pastoralists in the South, East, and West keep them for milk and meat production and for sale. Goats in the highlands are widely distributed in the crop-livestock production systems with very small flock sizes as a means of cash earnings and meat. Despite the huge resource potential, production and export opportunities, goat production in Nigerian is relatively undeveloped (Rege, 1992b).

Although there are severe environmental constraints to increase goat productivity, there is considerable potential for goat production in the country, where goat milk, meat, and skin are valued commodities (Rege, 1992b).

2.14 MOLECULAR MARKER AND THEIR TECHNIQUES STUDIED

Genetic marker is a broad term for any visible or assayable phenotype or the genetic basis for the assessment of the observed phenotypic variability. Genetic markers are classified based on visually evaluated traits (morphological and productive traits). Molecular marker is a term used to refer to a specific DNA variation between individuals that has been found to be associated with certain characteristics. These variations include insertions, deletions, translocations, duplications, and point mutations. They have characteristic biological properties that can be detected and measured in any parts of the body such as the blood or tissue at any stage (Deb, Singh & Kumar, 2012)

DNA markers (molecular markers) are the most important tools added to the armory of the scientists to characterize, distinguish, or relate individuals within or between breeds, strains, or species. The advances of the last two decades in techniques on DNA polymorphism and subsequent data analysis have greatly increased the ability to understand the genetic relationship among species at the molecular level. DNA genetic markers have now been used for the molecular genetics characterization and genetic diversity studies in numerous species (Botstein *et al.*, 1980).

The DNA polymorphism to be used widely for genome characterization and analysis was restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) (Botstein, White, Skolnick & Davis, 1980). Large amount of data have been generated since the first demonstration of RFLP (Grodzicker, Williams, Sharp & Sambrook, 1974) and RFLP

have been used as markers in human genetics (Botstein *et al.*, 1980), in genetic improvement of plant (Tanksley, Young, Peterson & Bonierbale, 1989) and animals (Soller & Beckmann, 1982). The introduction of PCR in conjunction with the constantly increasing availability of DNA sequence data also represents a milestone in this endeavor.

A variety of different molecular techniques are now being used in various laboratories for the study of inter- and intra-specific genetic variation at the DNA level. The most widely used techniques are restriction fragment length polymorphism (Botstein *et al.*, 1980) of nuclear DNA and mitochondrial DNA, minisatellites probing, microsatellites PCR amplification, random amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD), amplified fragment length polymorphism (AFLP) and sequencing of mitochondrial DNA fragments (Cunningham, Loftus, MacHugh & Bradley, 1994). These techniques differ in the type of data they generate, in the way that they resolve genetic variations and in the taxonomic levels at which they may be most appropriate.

2.14.1 Random Amplified Polymorphic DNA (RAPD)

Random amplified polymorphic DNA markers were developed in the early 1990s (Williams, Kubelik, Livak, Rafalski & Tingey, 1990). The RAPD polymorphisms are based on mismatches in primer binding sites or insertion/deletion events and therefore usually result in the presence or absence of an amplified product from a single locus. RAPD involves the use of a single and short arbitrary primer which can be synthesized or are available commercially. Using of such primer in PCR amplification results in several discrete DNA band products. Each product is derived from a region of the genome that contains two short segments in inverted orientation, on opposite strands that are complementary to the primer and sufficiently close together for amplification to work. More particularly this technique utilizes random

10-base oligonucleotide as primer to amplify discrete fragments of genomic DNA through PCR (Williams *et al.*, 1990) i.e. in contrast to using two specific primers as used in a conventional PCR for amplification of a specific region in DNA. RAPD employs a single primer (10mer) to amplify DNA of any genome region that happens to be flanked in opposite orientation within 5000 bp of each other. During the annealing step the primer anneals to the template at two sites on complementary strand of DNA template. If these priming sites are within an amplifiable range of each other, discrete DNA product is formed through the amplification.

In RAPD, the amplification products are separated on agarose gels in the presence of ethidium bromide and the resultant bands are visualized under ultraviolet light (Williams *et al.*, 1990). The presence of bands can be scored and the data converted into similarity matrices for calculation of genetic distances. RAPD method has opened a new area of genetic analysis due to its relative simplicity and speed. It is being applied widely in livestock animals for various purposes such as breed characterization (Yadav, Thakur, Singhal & Singh, 2001), species identification, parentage testing, and pedigree analysis, population studies and detection of genetic variations.

The advantages of RAPD are that there is no requirement for DNA probes or sequence information for the design of primers, the procedure is quick, simple and can be automated, and very small amount of DNA (e.g. 10ng per reaction) is required, moreover this technique does not require any restriction enzyme and radioactivity, and the technique is cheaper (Kantanen, Vilkki, Elo & Maki-Tanila, 1995). Disadvantages of RAPD are however many. First, RAPD methods are very sensitive to the PCR reaction conditions, DNA quality and PCR temperature profiles. It is absolutely critical to maintain strictly constant PCR conditions in order to achieve

reproducible results. Second, the markers are dominant, thus heterozygotes cannot be detected. Third, in the absence of pedigree analysis, the identity of individual bands in the multi-band profiles is not known and there can be uncertainty in assigning markers to specific loci. This makes it difficult to use RAPD in inter-population or interspecific Comparisons (Dowling, Moritz, Palmer & Rieseberg, 1996). Fourth, single bands on the gel can sometimes be comprised of several co-migrating amplification products.

2.14.2 Isozymes and Enzymes

Isozymes are multiple molecular forms of individual enzymes. These multiple forms can be alleles of one another at a single locus allozymes or can be products of different loci where there are multiple copies of genes making the same enzyme or enzyme sub- units. Temporal differences in isozyme expression exist, which can be utilized in the study of developmental genetics – spatial or tissue-specific expression as well as allelic variation. Isozyme and enzyme analyses are technically easy, but are limited in both the numbers of loci available and polymorphism. For example, the most isozyme characters, if two terminal non-sister taxa have lost the expression of an enzymes locus independently, then the probability of a homoplastic loss of the pleomorphic state is 100% (Murphy, 1993).

2.14.3 Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (RFLP)

Polymorphism at the DNA sequence level is often detected as a variation in length of restriction fragments produced by cutting DNA with restriction enzyme (Botstein *et al.*, 1980). Such polymorphism is referred to as RFLP and the first genetic map of the human genome was produced using this technique in the year 1980. RFLP is the result of differences in the sequence of nucleotides in the DNA of individual animal. These differences are the result of mutations in the genome occurring over

time and are detected as variations (polymorphism) in length of restriction fragments. In RFLP, DNA is digested with restriction enzymes that cut DNA at particular sites within a specific recognition sequence, typically of 4-6 base pairs (bp) long (Dowling *et al.*, 1996). Since each enzyme cleaves DNA at a characteristic recognition sequence, the complete digestion of a particular DNA produces an array of fragments. These fragments are separated by gel electrophoresis and blotted onto a filter and then probes are hybridized to the DNA. Variations in fragment lengths between individuals, populations or species, are results of mutation, which either alter restriction sites or lead to insertions/deletions of cleavage sites. Such polymorphism in a specific gene locus can be used to distinguish animal species, populations and individuals. The advantages are that RFLPs give highly reproducible band patterns and are co-dominant markers, hence, heterozygotes are distinguishable. The limitations of RFLPs are that, it is labor intensive and relatively expensive, as a good supply of probes is needed and the blotting and hybridization steps are time-consuming, and difficult to automate. Also the extent of detectable polymorphism may be limited for intra-species comparison and sufficient quantities (e.g. 10µg per digestion) of good quality DNA are required. Because of the last limitation, RFLPs are not applicable when very limited amount of source material or preserved tissues are available (Dowling *et al.*, 1996).

2.14.4 Amplified Fragment Length Polymorphism (AFLP)

The AFLP method is a more recent PCR based technique (Vos *et al.*, 1995), which is essentially intermediate between RFLPs and RAPDs. In AFLPs, the first step involves restriction digestion of the genomic DNA and the oligonucleotide adapters are ligated to the ends of the restricted fragments. The second step involves selective amplification of sets of restriction fragments. Either a pre-selection step is performed

using magnetic beads followed by a round of selective PCR or two selective rounds of PCR amplification are applied (Vos *et al.*, 1995). In the last step, the amplified products are separated by polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis and can be visualized using radioactive or fluorescent labeling. Compared to RAPDs, AFLP results are much more easily reproducible (Vos *et al.*, 1995). Compared with RFLPs, AFLPs are faster, less labour intensive and provide more information (Powell *et al.*, 1996). Because of their large genome coverage (on average they give 100 bands per gel compared with 20 for RAPDs), AFLPs are particularly good for mapping, and also fingerprinting and genetic distances can be calculated between genotypes. However, AFLPs share many of the limitations, with respect to band homologies and identities, as RAPDs, for example as RAPD bands, AFLP are co-dominant markers.

2.14.5 Mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) Analysis

Mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) sequence differences among individuals or populations can be assayed indirectly through restriction site analysis (Loftus *et al.*, 1994) or directly through DNA sequencing (Cunningham *et al.*, 1994). The former is often less expensive and allows rapid screening of large samples. The latter provides often more information as all changes at the nucleotide level will be revealed. In restriction site analysis, isolated mtDNA is digested with a restriction enzyme and the resulting fragments separated by gel electrophoresis. Genotypes are comprised of the composite restriction fragment patterns following digestion with 10-20 restriction enzymes. The pattern of restriction site loss or gain among genotypes for a panel of restriction enzymes can be used to estimate genetic differentiation and evolutionary history of populations or species (Avis, 1994). In sequencing, mtDNA genes are directly sequenced using universal or species specific primers that allow amplification of sequences as much as several thousand base pairs in length. Since different genes

in the mtDNA genome evolved at different rates, rapidly evolving genes can be analyzed to determine the relationship of recently diverged populations, whereas slowly evolving genes can be used to answer systematic questions involving distantly related species (Cunningham *et al.*, 1994).

2.14.6 Variable Number of Tandem Repeats (VNTRs)

Throughout the genome of individuals there are many regions comprised of tandemly repeated simple sequences. These repeat sequences vary in number and hence in length and are generally called variable number of tandem repeats (VNTRs), although the terms minisatellites and microsatellite are used depending on the size of the sequence of base pairs which is repeated. Jeffreys, Wilson, Thein, Weatherall and Ponder (1986) first reported the term minisatellites. Minisatellites region are characterized by randomly repeating oligonucleotide units ranging from 10 to 60 bp in length whereas in microsatellite the repeated sequences are only 2 to 5 bp long (Queller, Strassmann & Hughes, 1993). Although variation in both systems is the result of change in copy number, the underlying mechanism of mutation and the chromosomal locations differ. Microsatellite loci are randomly distributed and subject to replication slippage while minisatellites loci tend to be concentrated near telomeres and their length vary following intra-molecular or intra-allelic recombination and gene conversion mechanisms (Jeffreys *et al.*, 1994).

2.14.7 Microsatellite

A microsatellite is a short, repetitive sequence of DNA. Since they tend to vary little between closely related organisms, microsatellites are often used by scientists as genetic markers to identify individuals that come from the same breeding population. They are also known as short tandem repeats (STRs), or variable number tandem repeats (VNTR) and simple sequence repeats (SSRs). If one thinks of a

molecule of DNA as resembling a ladder, then each rung in the ladder is made up of a pair of smaller molecules called nucleotides (Afroz, Faruque, Husain, Han & Paul, 2010). The four nucleotides that appear in DNA are adenine (A), guanine (G), thymine (T) and cytosine (C). Adenine pairs with thymine and guanine pairs with cytosine. The order in which these base pairs appear gives a strand of DNA its unique signature and constitutes a code that stores genetic information.

A microsatellite occurs when a short sequence of base pairs, usually between 1 and 6, repeats several times in a row (Udeh, 2015). The following illustration of a short strand of DNA shows a single microsatellite composed of the unit GTC on the top half and CAG on the bottom half, each repeated 4 times. Scientists would represent this as (GTC)₄ or (CAG)₄:

A microsatellite consists of a specific sequence of DNA bases or nucleotides which contains mono, di, tri, or tetra tandem repeats. For example,

AAAAAAAAAAAA would be referred to as (A)₁₁

GTGTGTGTGTGT would be referred to as (GT)₆

CTGCTGCTGCTG would be referred to as (CTG)₄

ACTCACTCACTCACTC would be referred to as (ACTC)₄

According to Kumar *et al.*, (2003) these groups of repeating sequences were named "microsatellites" because, when DNA is separated by spinning it in a centrifuge, it tends to group into a large main band surrounded by smaller, "satellite" bands. Researchers named the DNA they found in these bands mini-satellites and microsatellites. Mini-satellites are longer segments, which may consist of up to about

100 repeating base pairs. Microsatellite markers are often useful for identifying individuals from the same breeding population. Rarely, mutations occur when a genetic sequence is passed from a parent to offspring, resulting in more or fewer units of the repeating segment. Thus, in our example above, (CAG)₄ could become (CAG)₃ or (CAG)₅. These mutations occur often enough that a wild breeding population is likely to have different microsatellites than other breeding groups, but they occur infrequently enough that individuals within a single breeding group are likely to share certain characteristic sequences (Chen *et al.*, 2004).

Most microsatellites are found in non-coding DNA which does not have the "code" or instructions to manufacture protein. Consequently, they are not believed to play a significant role in cell functioning. There is reason to believe, however, that a microsatellite can disrupt normal cell processes if it grows too large. For instance, in the case of Huntington's disease, the number of repeats of a certain sequence can mean the difference between being affected by the disease, or being a non-affected carrier. Alleles at a specific location (locus) can differ in the number of repeats. Microsatellites are inherited in a Mendelian fashion. Okpeku *et al.* (2011b) employed microsatellite in their study and reported that Polymorphic information content of the markers averaged 0.803 and mean G_{st} index was 0.176, and concluded that the measure of genetic distance between pairs of breeds indicated that the lowest distance was between WAD and RS (0.268) and the highest distance was between WAD and SA (0.662) goats, respectively.

Efficiency of microsatellites

There have been several attempts in characterizing the local populations of livestock species using different types of molecular markers. For proper characterization of principal livestock species for the purpose of conserving superior

genotypes, it is advisable to use modern molecular markers called microsatellites. These markers are capable of revealing all the genetic information inherent in any species population and can be used to measure important genetic diversity indices. Among the several DNA-based methods available, microsatellite markers provide the best and most reliable results when used with plants and animals (Van Marle-Koster & Casey, 2001).

Recent information in literatures have revealed that microsatellite markers are useful in determining not only heterozygosity and estimating genetic distances among closely related species (Chen *et al.*, 2004), it is also suitable for measuring important parameters such as number of effective alleles (N_e) as well as the polymorphism information content (PIC) in populations and can detect unique alleles. Thus, use of microsatellite markers has become a standard method to estimate genetic diversity indices in all livestock species. Kumar *et al.*, (2003) in a study with Southern Asian cattle using microsatellite markers observed that Expected heterozygosity ranged from 0.60 to 0.72 while mean number of allele ranged from 4.40 to 6.55 and concluded that within the South Asian breeds, neither gene diversity (heterozygosity) nor MNA showed a discernible geographical pattern that could point to a likely region of origin.

2.15 CHARACTERIZATION OF ANIMALS GENETICS RESOURCES

Characterization of animal genetic resources encompasses all activities associated with the identification, quantitative and qualitative description and documentation of breed populations, their natural habitats and production systems to which they are or are not adapted to (FAO, 2007). The objective of characterization is to increase knowledge of Animal Genetic Resources (AnGR), their abundance, and potentials for future uses, in wider environments.

Characterization activities should contribute to objective and reliable prediction of animal performance in defined environments, so as to allow a comparison of the potential performance of different types of AnGR within the various production systems found in a country or region (FAO, 2015). Developing countries are endowed with the majority of the global domestic animal diversity-landraces, strains or breeds. Some livestock breeds in these countries are not characterized, their genetic resources are unknown, such that others are endangered, some had extricated, others that survived are either highly threatened or endangered through indiscriminate crossbreeding or destruction of the environment that enhanced their continued survival.

The importance of indigenous livestock breeds lies in their adaptation to local biotic and abiotic stresses and to traditional husbandry systems. However, most of these animal genetic resources are still not characterized and boundaries between distinct populations are unclear. In such case, breeds distinctions are defined on the basis of subjective data and information obtain from local communities (FAO, 2015). Reliance on these criteria as a basis for classification for utilization and/or conservation may be misleading, as historical evidences are not always accurate, relying as it often does, on subjective judgments. Archival research can reveal much about the original morphological type of a breed or strain but its molecular genetic evidence which is factual and precise cannot be characterize by this method. It is in this sphere that molecular characterization of animal genetic resources has an important role (Rege, 1995). Characterization is typically differentiated into two categories; phenotypic characterization and molecular characterization (FAO, 2015).

Molecular characterization explores polymorphism in selected protein molecules and DNA markers in order to measure genetic variations at the population

levels. Thus, DNA level polymorphisms are markers of choice for molecular characterization (FAO, 2007). The process of molecular characterization comprises field sampling of biological material (blood or hair root samples), laboratory extraction of DNA from the samples, DNA storage, laboratory assaying (genotyping or sequencing), data analysis, report writing and maintenance of information database (FAO, 2007). The laboratory results of molecular genetics are used in determining within and between-breed diversity parameters, identify the geographical locations of particular population, and or of admixture among population of different genetic origins, provide information on evolutionary relationship and clarify centre of origin and migration routes (FAO, 2007). Molecular genetics diversity indices are as follows:

2.15.1 Expected and Observed Heterozygosity

Heterozygosity deficiency is a situation where heterozygosity in alleles of a population is very low or absent which results to genetic similarity of the population. Very high deficit in heterozygosity is an indication of the presence of null alleles. Also, the deficit could probably reflect to subdivision of the whole population into breeds (SanCristobal, Chevalet, Foully & Olivier, 2003). Heterozygosity deficiency may result from one or more of the following reasons:

- i. The presence of null allele which is the allele that fails to multiply during PCR using a given genetic marker primers site.
- ii. Small sample size, where rare genotypes are likely to be included in the samples.
- iii. The Wahlund effect, i.e. presence of fewer heterozygotes in population than predicted on account of population subdivision.

- iv. The decrease in heterozygosity due to increased consanguinity (inbreeding) (Kumar *et al.*, 2006).

Kalinowski (2002) stated that high value of average expected heterozygosity within population can be obtained when there is large allele numbers in the loci tested. When the average direct count of heterozygosity in overall loci is less than the expected heterozygosity, then it implies that there is loss of heterozygosity in the population under consideration, and this will result to 'allele fixation. Genetic diversity within populations can be determined through observed and expected heterozygosities. These parameters can be determined using GENEPOP Package version 3.2 as described in Raymond and Rousset (1995).

2.15.2 Number and Frequency of Alleles

Genetic similarity and genetic distance between populations are obtained using allele frequencies considering all loci and the population. Number of alleles per locus per population can be determined by direct counting. The genetic diversity within each population is determined from the mean number of alleles per locus and average observed and expected heterozygosities. The observed number of alleles per locus demonstrates the degree of marker loci polymorphism in the population of animal.

The allele and genotypic frequencies are identified directly from the gel. Hardy-Weingberg equilibrium (HWE) is tested based on likelihood ratio for different locus in population combination. Genotypic frequency is used to test for deviation from HWE at each locus over all populations. A population is considered to be within HWE only when it is able to maintain its relative allele frequencies. Heterozygosis deficiency is one of the parameters underlying departure from Hardy-Weingberg equilibrium (Laval *et al.*, 2000).

2.15.3 Dendrogram or Phylogenetics or Cluster Diagram

Dendrogram is used to portray relationship between populations. Population or breeds that cluster together indicate close relationship. Phylogeny is constructed from genetic distance data, and breeds will be grouped according to their geographic locations of origin. Cluster diagram will show clearly how breeds are related or separated from each other. MacHugh, Shriver, Loftus, Cunningham and Bradley (1997) reported population clustering according to their geographic origin in cattle, and chicken. This implies that geographically adjacent populations are more genetically related, probably because of founder effects and interbreeding, especially around bordering geographic locations. However, morphological differences between populations are not taken into account by neutral molecular markers. Hence, breed relationships are more related to geographical location of the breeds than to the morphological differences between the breeds. Agaviezor *et al.* (2012) obtained two distinct clusters in Nigerian breeds of sheep and concluded that the differences found in the microsatellite data may indicate recent crossbreeding due to geographical closeness among the sympatric breeds, especially involving males from one breed crossing with females of the other breeds.

2.15.4 Polymorphism Information Content (PIC)

Polymorphism Information Content (PIC) is defined as the probability that the marker genotype of a given offspring will allow deduction, in the absence of crossing-over of which the two marker alleles of the affected parents the offspring received (Guo & Elston, 1999). The PIC value is often used to measure the informativeness of a genetic marker for linkage studies. The PIC value was first derived for the case of a rare dominant disease, when one of the parents is affected, and is a function of the particular mode of disease inheritance (Guo & Elston, 1999). Polymorphism

Information Content (PIC) is estimated in order to assess the relevance of each locus for linkage. It assesses the degree of polymorphism of all the markers in the whole populations (Ohwojakpor, Olowofeso, Adebambo and Onagbesan, 2012) obtained a very high mean PIC values across all loci that ranged from 0.7588 to 0.8282, indicating that all loci genotyped were highly informative. Also, observed number of alleles per locus demonstrates the degree of marker loci polymorphism in the animal population. Markers are said to be appropriate (polymorphic) for genetic distance when the number of alleles for each marker are higher than the minimum number of alleles (at least four alleles) recommended for genetic marker to be used in the estimate of genetic distance. Agaviezor *et al.* (2012) reported that Polymorphism Information Content (PIC) in 15 microsatellite loci demonstrated high polymorphism in the studied population with PIC values ranging from 0.751 to 0.927, lending strong support to the use of such panel of markers for assessing genetic diversity in Nigerian sheep. Okpeku *et al.* (2011) obtained PIC value of 0.803 in Preliminary analysis of microsatellite-based genetic diversity of goats in southern Nigeria.

2.15.5 Shannon's Index

Shannon's Index (H) is a commonly used diversity index that takes into account both abundance and evenness of species present in the community. It is explained by the formula:

$$H = \sum(P_i \times \ln P_i)$$

Where H = the Shannon diversity index

P_i = fraction of the entire population made up of species i (proportion of a species i relative to total number of species present, not encountered).

S = number of species encountered

Here, a high value of H would be a representative of a diverse and equally distributed community and lower values represent a community with just one species.

Shannon's Equitability (E_H) measures the evenness of a community and can be easily calculated by dividing the value of H with H_{\max} , which equals to $\ln S$ (S = number of species encountered). Its value ranges between 0 and 1, with 1 being the complete evenness.

$$E_H = H / H_{\max} = H / \ln S \text{ (Begon, Herper \& Townseed, 1996).}$$

2.15.6 Genetic Distance

According to Udeh (2015) genetic distance refers to the genetic divergence between species or between populations within a species. It is measured by a variety of parameters. Smaller genetic distances indicate a close genetic relationship whereas large genetic distances indicate a more distant genetic relationship. Genetic distance can be used to compare the genetic similarity between different species, such as humans and chimpanzees. Within a species genetic distance can be used to measure the divergence between different sub-species (Afroz *et al.*, 2010; Anita & Yadav, 2007). In its simplest form, the genetic distance between two populations is the difference in frequencies of a trait. There are several measures used to indicate genetic distance. A commonly used measure of genetic distance is the fixation index which varies between 0 and 1 a value of 0 indicates that two populations are genetically identical whereas a value of 1 indicates that two populations are different species.

The Nei's standard genetic distance is measure assumes that genetic differences arise due to mutations and genetic drift (Nei, 1972). This measure assumes that genetic differences arise due to genetic drift only. (Cavalli-Sforza & Edwards 1967, Reynolds *et al.*, 1983) while Nei's (D_A) genetic distance is distance assumes that genetic differences arise due to mutations and genetic drift, but this distance measure is known to give more reliable population trees than other distances particularly for microsatellite DNA data (Takezaki & Nei, 1996).

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 LOCATION OF THE STUDY

This study was conducted in eight locations (Ungogo, Kumbotso, Dala, Kano Municipal, Wudil, Bebeji, Rimin Gado and Tofa) in Kano State. Kano State is located in the semi-arid area of North-western Nigeria at an elevation of 468.5m (1537.07 ft) above sea level. Kano has a subtropical stepped climate the city yearly temperature is 30.75°C and it is 1.29% higher than Nigerians average. Kano typically receives about 49.8mm of precipitation and has 62.99 raining days annually. It has a population of 15,076,892 (NPC, 2006). Kano State is the commercial nerve Centre of Northern Nigeria. It is located between latitude 10°33' and 12°27' North of the equator and longitude 7°34' and 9°29' East of the Greenwich meridian and as such it is part of Sudan-Sahel vegetation zone of Nigeria. It has a hot semi-arid steppe climate which exhibits a tropical wet-dry season with a mono-modal rainfall distribution (NIMET, 2021). Kano State occupies a total land area of about 42,582.8 km² out of which 754,200 ha is being used for agricultural production while forest and grazing land occupy 75,000 ha. The pattern of animal rearing in the study location includes keeping both ruminant and non-ruminant animals.

3.2 EXPERIMENTAL ANIMALS AND MANAGEMENT

Three hundred and seventy four (374) goats from eight (8) selected locations in Kano State were used for the study. Hence, the four breeds considered in this study are Sahel goat, Kano Brown, Red Sokoto and West African Dwarf goat. Blood samples were collected from these breeds in eight locations in Kano state. The experimental animals were managed under semi-intensive system by their owners. The goat houses were made using corn stalk for fencing and thatched roofing for

protection against temperature and rainfall in all the locations. There was no organized health care provision in terms of vaccination and deworming. They were allowed to roam in search of food and water alone with their kids. Age of the animal ranges from 2- 4 years was determined from its teeth. Body weight was taken by weighing scale (kg) and morphometric measurements were taken by measuring tape (cm).

Table 1. Sample Size of Animal per Breed, Location, Sex and Age

Location	Sahel	Kano Brown	Red Sokoto	WAD	Male	Female	Age
Ungogo	15	20	4	11	21	29	2-4
Kumbotso	10	30	2	10	22	30	2-4
Dala	15	22	2	15	24	30	2-4
Wudil	16	25	3	5	20	29	2-4
Tofa	10	10	4	10	14	20	2-4
Rimin gado	16	15	2	15	22	26	2-4
Bebeji	10	18	2	16	20	26	2-4
Kano Municipal	10	11	2	18	12	29	2-4
Total	102	151	21	100	155	219	

3.3 MORPHOLOGICAL MEASUREMENTS

The Body weight and fourteen (14) Morphological measurements were taken from each of the 374 adult (155 male & 219 female) Goats population (KNB=151, RSK=21, SHL=102 & WAD=100) using kilogram and measuring tape according to the procedures of Akpa, Ambali and Suleiman (2013). The male and female goats were restrained properly while taken the measurement to prevent error. The following morphometric traits that were taken include:

Table 2. Morphometric Traits and their Description

Morphometric Traits (cm)	Description
Head Circumference (HC)	Measures the circumference of the head.
Hip Height (HH)	Measures vertical distance from the floor to the highest point in the hook region or pelvic girdle.
Neck Length (NL)	Measures the region of cervical vertebrae
Ear Length (EL)	Measures from the point where the ear is attached to tip.
Horn Length (HL)	Measures from the point of attachment of the horn to the head up to tip.
Tail Length (TL)	Measures the distance from the beginning of caudal vertebra up to tip.
Wither Height (WH)	Measures vertical distance from the floor to the top of the shoulder.
Cannon Length (CL)	Measures the length of the cannon.
Chest Depth (CD)	Measures the distance from the lowest point of the wither region up to the sternum.
Body Length (BL)	Measures distance from shoulder point to the point of pin bone of tail region.
Heart Girth (HG)	Measures body circumference, slightly behind shoulder and perpendicular to body axis.
Face Length (FL)	Measures the length of the face.
Gonadal Length (GL)	Measures the length of the gonadal from point of attachment to the body to the tip.
Gonadal Circumference (GC)	Measures the circumference of gonadal.

3.4 SAMPLE COLLECTION AND HANDLING

Twenty- four (24) blood samples were randomly collected from eight selected locations across Kano state. Six (6) blood samples were collected per 3 breeds per sex (Sahel, Red Sokoto, Kano brown and West African Dwarf). The blood samples were

collected from jugular vein of the animal, 5ml of blood was collected aseptically from each animal into an EDTA tubes, using 23 gauge sterile needles and syringes, and was stored at -20°C by using (ethylene-di-amine tetra ethl acetic acid, EDTA) as anticoagulant. The samples were transported to the National Veterinary Research Institute (NVRI) Laboratory Vom for analysis in an ice pack loaded with ice blocks to maintain the required temperature. On arrival at the laboratory, the samples were immediately transferred to refrigerator while reagents and apparatus were prepared for DNA extractions and subsequent laboratory analysis (Akpa, Ambali & Suleiman 2013).

3.5 LABORATORY ANALYSIS

The samples were genetically analyzed at National Veterinary Research Institute Vom Jos, Plateau state. All the experimental procedures were carried out in accordance to the guidelines of the laboratory.

3.6 PROCEDURE FOR DNA EXTRACTION

This study was undertaken on four (4) different breeds of goats in Kano State. The Genomic DNA was isolated from samples using quick DNA miniport plus kit™ (Zymo, 2021).

3.6.1 The Procedure for DNA Extraction according to quick DNA miniport plus kit (Zymo, 2021) are as follows:

- i. A 200µl samples was added to a micro centrifuged tube, 200µl Biofluid and cell buffer (RED) with 20µl proteinase K was also added.
- ii. Thoroughly mixed for 15 seconds and the tube was incubated at 55°C for 10 minutes.
- iii. One volume of genomic binding buffer was added to the digested sample and mixed thoroughly for 15 seconds.

- iv. A mixture was transferred into a Zymo-Spin™ 11C-XLR Column in a collection tube centrifuged at 12,000 x g for 1 minute. The collection tube with the flow through was discarded.
- v. A 400µl DNA pre-wash buffer was added into the spin column in a new collection and centrifuged at 12,000 x g for 1 minute. The collection tube was emptied.
- vi. A 700µl g-DNA wash Buffer was added into the spin column and centrifuged at 12,000 x g for 1 minute. The collection tube was emptied.
- vii. A 200µl g-DNA wash Buffer was again added into the spin column and then centrifuged at 12,000 x g for 1 minute. The collection tube with the flow through was discarded.
- viii. The spin column was finally transferred into a clean micro centrifuged tube, and then 50µl⁴ DNA elution buffer was added directly on the matrix and incubate for 5 minutes at room temperature, then centrifuged at maximum speed of 14000RPM for 1 minute to elute the DNA⁶. The eluted DNA were used immediately for molecular based application and stored - 20⁰c for future used.

3.7 POLYMERASE CHAIN REACTION

3.7.1 DNA Amplification

A master mix was prepared that contained 25µl reaction volume which includes: 9.5µl volume of nuclease free water, 12.5µl of 2XMM and 1.0µl of primers (10picamol) and then 2µl of DNA Template sample was added to each of the PCR tube so as to make the final volume of 25µl. In order to detect any contamination, negative control was set up without genomic DNA

The samples were placed in a thermocycler using the following settings: an initial denaturation at 95°C (3minutes), denaturation of 95°C (45 seconds), annealing at 58°C (45 seconds), extension at 75°C (45 seconds) and final extension at 72°C (10minutes) 4α for 35 cycles for primer ILSTS087, OarFeb48 & ILSTS011 while primer ILSTS005 and MAF70 are annealing temperature at 55°C and 65°C respectively (Zymo, 2021).

3.7.2 Gel Electrophoresis

After amplification, PCR product was run on a 1.5% agrose gel electrophoresis, stained with ethidium bromide and visualized by ultra-violet light, Bands of the corrected sizes was excised from the gel and documented.

Five microsatellite markers were used to genotype in order to standardize allele scoring amongst gels. The exact allele sizes were determined by direct comparisons with the adjacent PCR band known DNA sample and 50bp ladder. (Zymo, 2021). The primers were used as microsatellite markers chosen from FAO recommended list as presented in table 2 with their relevant information and obtained from Inqaba Biotech West Africa.

Table 3. Lists of Primers with their relevant informations

Locus	Repeat Array	Primer Sequence 5'-3'	Genebank Accession Number	MgCL ₂ (Mm)	Annealing Temperature (°C)	Range of Base Pair (Expected)	Expected Allele Number
ILSTS087	(CA) ₁₄	AGCAGACATGATGACTCAGC CTGCCTCTTTTCTTGAGAG	L37279	1.875	58	135-153	5
OarFeb48	(AC) ₁₄	GAGTTAGTACAAGGATGACAAGAGGCAC GACTCTAGAGGATCGCAAAGAACCAG	M82875	1.875	58	152-164	8
ILSTS011	(CA) ₁₁	GCTTGCTACATGGAAAGTGC CTAAAATGCAGAGCCCTACC	L23485	1.875	58	262-280	7
ILSTS005	(nn) ₃₉	GGAAGCAATTGAAATCTATAGCC TGTTCTGTGAGTTTGTAAGC	L23481	2.0	55	152-218	4
MAF70	(AC) ₃₉	CACGGAGTCACAAAGAGTCAGACC GCAGGACTCTACGGGGCCTTTGC	M77199	1.0	65	134-168	7

Source: FAO (2007)

3.8 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The data from the body weight and morphometric measurements were computed in excel and analysed using GLM procedures of SAS 9.4, (2000), and Duncan Multiple Range Test was used to separate the means. Simple linear Regression ($Y = a+bx$) was used to determine the relationship between length and weight. Pearson correlation was used to determine the relationships among variables (SAS, 2000). It has a value between +1 and -1, where 1 is total positive linear correlation, 0 is no linear correlation, and -1 is total negative linear correlation. Dendrogram was constructed using morphometric measurements to determine the genetic distance among populations. The following statistical models were used for the analysis of morphometric characters:

$$Y_{ijkl} = \mu + C_i + X_j + S_k + P_l + E_{ijkl}$$

$$Y_{ijkl} = \text{Morphometric Characteristics}$$

Where μ = Population mean

C_i = Fixed effect of i^{th} breed ($i = 1$ -Kano Brown, 2-West African Dwarf, 3-Red Sokoto and 4-Sahelian)

X_j = Fixed effect of j^{th} sex ($j = 1$ - male and 2- female)

S_k = Fixed effect of k^{th} location ($k = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 \& 8$)

P_l = Effects of l^{th} age ($l = 2, 3 \& 4$)

E_{ijkl} = Error term (random error)

Allele frequencies for each locus within each sampled population were computed. This was calculated locus by locus with the expression:

$$freqAllele - x = \frac{2N_{xx} + N_{xy}}{2N}$$

Where N_{xx} is the number of homozygotes for allele X (XX), and N_{xy} is the number of heterozygotes containing the allele X (Y was any other allele to be tested).

N = the number of samples. These were tested for deviation of observed genotype frequencies from those under Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium using the Markov chain exact tests provided in the Genepop software (Raymond and Rousset, 1995). Estimate of microsatellite diversity within populations such as total alleles TNA, mean number of alleles MNA, allelic richness Ar, observed and expected (H_o and H_e) heterozygote as well as nuclear pairwise F_t , values corrected for multiple testing was calculated using MS analyser 4.05 (Dierienner and Schloetterer, 2003). Genetix (Belkher *et al.*, 2004) was used to infer genetic inbreeding coefficient F_{is} . To quantify the extent of molecular variation, locus-by-locus analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA) was performed using Genealex 6.4. In the current study, F_{st} was used to determine the potential differences between the two statistics. F-statistics were obtained using AMOVA approach and population pairwise based on microsatellite loci as implemented in Genealex 6.4. Genetic Distance were calculated by choosing the option *Distance* from the GenALEX menu and then selected *Genetic* from the submenu. It was ensured that locus and sample parameters were correct in the Genetic Distance Options dialog box. Then the appropriate Distance Calculation was selected and output options required. Title and Worksheet Prefix was entered and then click Ok. Genetic distance was output to sheet.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 RESULTS

4.1.1 Morphological Characterization of Indigenous Breed of Goat

Table 4 shows the descriptive statistic of the Morphometric trait measured for the goats. The result showed that the body weight of indigenous breeds of goats range from 43.59kg to 48.75kg with the means body weight of 46.17kg and the coefficient variation of 20.61% and the least of 10.45cm to 11.48cm.

Table 4: Summary Statistics for Body weight (kg) and Morphometric Characteristics Measured (cm)

Parameters	Mean \pm SE	CV (%)	Min	Max
BW	46.17 \pm 1.30	20.61	43.59	48.75
BL	52.12 \pm 0.53	7.53	51.08	53.16
HG	65.91 \pm 0.80	8.94	64.34	67.49
WH	54.49 \pm 1.03	12.74	52.45	56.52
HH	55.81 \pm 1.42	16.87	53.00	58.63
HL	15.01 \pm 0.22	11.30	14.59	15.44
EL	18.24 \pm 0.38	16.51	17.49	18.98
CD	15.44 \pm 0.22	10.48	15.00	15.88
CL	32.13 \pm 0.45	11.59	31.23	33.03
HC	30.07 \pm 0.95	19.54	28.19	31.95
NL	19.28 \pm 0.31	10.98	18.67	19.89
TL	10.97 \pm 0.26	17.01	10.45	11.48
FL	16.55 \pm 0.24	10.18	16.07	17.04
GL	12.29 \pm 0.34	18.46	11.62	12.97
GC	18.45 \pm 0.39	13.37	17.69	19.22

SE= standard error, CV= coefficient variation, BW= body weight, BL= body length, HG= hearth girth, WH = Withers Height, HH= hip height, HL= horn length, EL= ear length, CD= chest depth, CL= Canon length, HC= head circumferences, NL= neck length, TL= tail length, FL= face length, GL= gonadal length, GC= gonadal circumference

Tables 5a and 5b shows the morphometric attributes of goat population in relation to breed. In kano brown, the average body weight was 46.17kg while 20.00kg found in crossed of kano brown and West African dwarf. Furthermore, average body of Red Sokoto was 43.07kg and it was 41.85kg in Sahelian goat with West African dwarf weight 33.91kg respectively. This means that kano brown weight highest with least in West African dwarf. Other morphometric traits measured were all highly significant ($p < 0.01$) except tail length and gonadal length that showed non-significant ($p > 0.05$) difference.

Tables 6a and 6b result shows the morphometric attributes of goat populations in relation to location. All the morphometric traits measured showed highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$) except tail length that had no significant difference with Bebeji having the highest body weight of 49.02kg followed by Kumbotso with 47.95kg while Kano Municipal weighted 47.05kg and Wudil with average body weight of 46.29kg. Goats from Dala had 41.37kg and Rimin Gado, Ungogo & Tofa weighted 33.67kg, 32.60kg and 32.46kg respectively.

Table 5a: Body weight (kg): Morphometric Attributes (cm) of Goat Population in Relation to Breed

Breed	BW	BL	HG	WH	HH	HL	EL	CD
KB	46.17±1.30 ^a	52.12±0.53 ^a	65.91±0.80 ^a	54.49±1.03 ^b	55.81±1.42 ^c	15.01±0.22 ^b	18.24±0.38	15.44±0.22 ^a
RS	43.07±2.72 ^b	50.02±1.10 ^b	66.13±1.66 ^a	60.41±2.14 ^a	57.57±2.96 ^{ab}	14.80±0.45 ^b	14.85±0.79	14.22±0.46 ^b
SH	41.85±1.35 ^c	49.80±0.55 ^c	64.39±0.82 ^b	60.79±1.07 ^a	59.14±1.47 ^a	16.27±0.22 ^a	15.48±0.39	15.82±0.23 ^a
WAD	33.91±1.40 ^d	48.24±0.56 ^d	59.64±0.85 ^c	53.45±1.10 ^c	48.07±1.53 ^d	16.16±0.23 ^a	12.79±0.41	12.27±0.24 ^c
P-Value	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01

a,b,c,d,e means within the same Column and factors with difference superscript within the specific dentition group are significant different (P<0.01), KB= Kano brown, WAD= west African dwarf, RS= red Sokoto, SH= sahel, BW= body weight, BL= body length, HG= hearth girth, WH = wither height, HH= hip height, HL= horn length , EL= ear length, CD= chest depth.

Table 5b: Morphometric Attributes (cm) of Goat Population in Relation to Breed

Breed	CL	HC	NL	TL	FL	GL	GC
KB	32.13±0.45 ^a	30.07±0.95 ^d	19.28±0.31 ^b	10.97±0.26	16.55±0.24 ^a	12.29±0.34	18.45±0.39 ^b
RS	24.98±0.95 ^c	34.93±1.98 ^b	21.16±0.64 ^a	11.04±0.54	15.32±0.51 ^b	13.50±0.071	18.22±0.80 ^b
SH	33.11±0.47 ^a	32.34±0.98 ^c	19.98±0.32 ^b	10.97±0.27	17.25±0.25 ^a	25.69±0.35	20.54±0.40 ^a
WAD	27.45±0.49 ^b	27.52±1.02 ^e	18.23±0.33 ^b	10.73±0.28	14.71±0.26 ^b	11.84±0.36	20.72±0.41 ^a
P-Value	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	0.3034	< 0.01	0.0580	< 0.01

a,b,c,d,e means within the same Column and factors with difference superscript within the specific dentition group are significant different (P<0.01), KB= Kano brown, WAD= West African dwarf, RS= Red Sokoto, SH= sahel, CL= Canon length , HC= head circumferences , NL= neck length, TL= tail length, FL= face length, GL= gonadal length, GC= gonadal circumference

Table 6a: Body weight (kg) and Morphometric Attributes (cm) of Goat Population in Relation to Location

Location	BW	BL	HG	WH	HH	HL	EL	CD
BBJ	49.02±2.29 ^a	51.19±0.92 ^a	69.41±1.39 ^a	64.69±1.81 ^a	60.33±2.50 ^b	15.72±0.38	19.14±0.66 ^a	13.85±0.39 ^d
Dala	41.37±1.73 ^c	48.29±0.70 ^b	64.71±1.06 ^b	57.18±1.37 ^c	55.61±1.89 ^c	16.44±0.29	14.78±0.30 ^{bc}	13.02±0.30 ^d
KBSO	47.95±1.81 ^b	51.59±0.73 ^a	68.29±1.11 ^{ab}	62.85±1.43 ^b	58.44±1.98 ^{bc}	16.49±0.030	15.29±0.53 ^b	16.29±0.31 ^a
KMC	47.05±1.73 ^b	50.37±0.70 ^{ab}	68.49±1.05 ^{ab}	62.64±1.36 ^b	57.02±1.89 ^{bc}	15.66±0.29	16.37±0.50 ^b	14.14±0.30 ^c
RMG	33.67±2.55 ^d	49.74±1.03 ^b	58.11±1.56 ^c	59.43±2.02 ^{bc}	63.60±2.79 ^a	15.60±0.42	15.52±0.74 ^b	15.43±0.44 ^b
Tofa	32.46±2.64 ^d	50.13±1.06 ^{ab}	56.83±1.61 ^d	42.58±2.08 ^e	43.21±2.88 ^d	14.63±0.44	13.62±0.76	13.71±0.45 ^d
UNG	32.60±1.84 ^d	49.62±0.74 ^b	53.30±1.12 ^d	52.28±1.45 ^d	54.63±2.01 ^c	14.84±0.30	14.26±0.53 ^{bc}	14.23±0.31 ^c
WDL	46.29±3.84 ^b	48.46±1.55 ^b	68.79±2.34 ^{ab}	52.25±3.03 ^d	41.63±4.19 ^e	15.96±0.63	13.17±1.11 ^c	17.30±0.66 ^a
P-Value	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01

a,b,c,d,e means within the same Column and factors with difference superscript within the specific dentition group are significant different (P<0.01), BW= body weight, BL= body length, HG= hearth girth, WH = wither height, HH= hip height, HL= horn length , EL= ear length, CD= chest depth, BBJ= bebeji, Dala, KBSO=kumbotso, KMC= Kano Municipal, RMG= riming ado, Tofa, UNG= ungogo, WDL= wudil.

Table 6b: Morphometric Attributes (cm) of Goat Population in Relation to Location

Location/Variables	CL	HC	NL	TL	FL	GL	GC
BBJ	39.00±0.80 ^a	34.63±1.66 ^a	21.35±0.54 ^a	10.97±0.26	16.55±0.24 ^a	10.74±0.39 ^c	20.54±0.68 ^c
Dala	22.27±0.60 ^d	29.11±1.26 ^c	17.88±0.41 ^c	11.04±0.54	15.32±0.51 ^b	13.68±0.45 ^{bc}	21.06±0.51 ^b
KBSO	32.16±0.63 ^c	27.24±1.32 ^d	19.54±0.53 ^b	11.00±1.81	17.25±0.25 ^a	14.89±0.47 ^b	23.84±0.34 ^a
KMC	34.72±0.60 ^b	31.79±1.26 ^b	21.29±0.41 ^a	10.97±0.27	14.71±0.26 ^b	11.70±0.45 ^c	20.37±0.51 ^b
RMG	32.36±0.89 ^c	34.19±1.86 ^a	19.64±0.60 ^b	10.73±0.28	12.00±1.71 ^c	11.31±0.66 ^c	21.09±0.61 ^b
Tofa	20.04±0.92 ^f	30.79±1.92 ^b	18.08±0.62 ^c	11.07±0.11	14.26±0.17 ^b	11.33±0.69 ^c	20.55±0.61 ^c
UNG	24.75±0.64 ^e	33.48±1.34 ^{ab}	18.74±0.43 ^c	11.12±0.13	13.69±0.18 ^{bc}	11.52±0.48 ^c	21.80±0.53 ^b
WDL	33.00±1.34 ^c	19.79±2.79 ^e	19.42±0.90 ^b	10.81±0.42	12.69±0.71 ^{bc}	16.96±0.99 ^a	23.80±0.55 ^a
P-Value	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	0.0343	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01

a,b,c,d,e means within the same Column and factors with difference superscript within the specific dentition group are significant different (P<0.01), CL= Canon length , HC= head circumferences , NL= neck length, TL= tail length, FL= face length, GL= gonadal length, GC= gonadal circumference, BBJ= bebeji, Dala, KBSO= kumbotso, KMC= Kano Municipal, RMG= riming ado, Tofa, UNG= ungoto, WDL= wudil.

Tables 7a and 7b shows morphometric attributes (cm) of goat population in relation to age and sex. The effect of age on the average body of the goat was 42.54kg at the age of 3 while weight 41.64kg at the age of 4 with the least of 38.58kg at the age of 2 respectively. Age has significant differences ($P < 0.05$) on the body weight and some linear measurements except for HH, HI, EL, HC, NL, TL, FL, GL and GC. Age effect shows that as age increase body weight other linear body measurements were increased. Sexual dimorphism in this study shows that male weight highest of 40.9kg that the female counterpart which weight at 36.48kg. The linear body measurements such as BL, HG, WH, HH, CL, HC, FL and GC had significant ($P < 0.01$) difference while HL, EL, CD, NL, TL and GL had non-significant value.

Tables 8a and 8b shows the interaction effect of morphometric attribute of goat population in relation to factors. There was significant ($P < 0.05$) difference for body weight, BL, HG, WH, CL, HH, HC and GC while the two ways interaction effect factors significant difference ($P > 0.05$) were not observed in HL, EL, CD, TL, FL and GL respectively.

Tables 9a, 9b and 9c show, the Pearson correlation matrix for all the trait measured from all the breed of goats studied. The relationship between the body weight and all the morphometric measurement were positive and significant ($p < 0.01$) except HC. The morphometric measure with negative and significant correlated were CD/HC ($r = -0.18$), GL/HC ($r = -0.37$) and FL/HC ($r = -0.33$). The remaining morphometric measurement had positive and significant relationship with correlated (r) value ranging from 0.17 for WH/CD to 0.63 for WH/NL.

Table 7a: Body Weight: Morphometric Attributes (cm) of Goat Population in Relation to Age and Sex

Variables factors	BW	BL	HG	WH	HH	HL	EL	CD
Age (years)								
2	38.58±1.30 ^b	49.38±0.53 ^b	61.44±0.79 ^b	57.10±1.03 ^a	55.05±1.42	15.16±0.22	14.96±0.38	13.95±0.22 ^b
3	42.54±1.37 ^a	51.21±0.55 ^a	63.73±0.84 ^a	56.07±1.08 ^b	55.39±1.50	16.13±0.23	15.48±0.40	15.13±0.23 ^a
4	41.64±1.32 ^a	49.47±0.53 ^b	64.76±0.81 ^a	57.91±1.04 ^a	55.02±1.44	15.59±0.22	15.87±0.38	14.54±0.23 ^b
P-Value	0.0013	0.0015	0.0007	0.0002	0.4231	0.5516	0.0335	<0.01
Sex								
Male	40.90±0.77 ^a	50.03±0.31 ^a	63.26±0.47 ^a	57.00±0.61 ^a	55.16±0.84 ^a	15.63±0.13	15.43±0.22	14.54±0.13
Female	36.48±0.66 ^b	42.62±0.23 ^b	59.11±0.36 ^b	54.66±0.53 ^b	52.11±0.71 ^b	14.77±0.11	15.26±0.17	13.96±0.10
P-Value	0.0096	0.0067	0.0049	0.0066	0.0088	0.1676	0.7334	0.3348

a,b,c,d,e means within the same Column and factors with difference superscript within the specific dentition group are significant different (P<0.01), BW= body weight, BL= body length, HG= hearth girth, WH = wither height, HH= hip height, HL= horn length , EL= ear length, CD= chest depth, age 2=2years, age 3= 3years, age 4= 4years.

Table 7b: Morphometric Attributes (cm) of Goat Population in Relation to Age and Sex

Variables factors	CL	HC	NL	TL	FL	GL	GC
Age (years)							
2	29.25±0.45 ^b	31.90±0.95 ^a	19.03±0.31	10.96±0.26	15.68±0.24	12.12±0.34	19.67±0.38
3	32.13±0.48 ^a	29.91±0.99 ^c	19.34±0.32	10.79±0.27	16.59±0.26	12.87±0.36	20.06±0.41
4	28.69±0.46 ^b	30.95±0.96 ^b	20.14±0.31	11.01±0.26	15.93±0.25	12.39±0.34	19.27±0.39
P-Value	0.0006	0.0023	0.0111	0.6809	0.0750	0.4745	0.1037
Sex							
Male	30.06±0.27 ^a	30.92±0.56 ^a	19.48±0.18 ^a	10.92±0.15	16.07±0.14	12.46±0.20	19.67±0.23 ^a
Female	27.77±0.21 ^b	28.04±0.33 ^b	18.97±0.11 ^b	10.09±0.14	14.22±0.09 ^b	11.93±0.16	17.02±0.19 ^b
P-Value	0.0039	0.0034	0.0002	0.9756	0.0030	0.0110	0.0024

a,b,c,d,e means within the same Column and factors with difference superscript within the specific dentition group are significant different (P<0.01), CL= Canon length , HC= head circumferences , NL= neck length, TL= tail length, FL= face length, GL= gonadal length, GC= gonadal circumference, age 2=2years, age 3= 3years, age 4= 4years.

Table 8a: Two Ways Interaction Effect of Body Weight (kg) and Morphometric Attributes (cm) in Relation to Factors

Interaction/variables	BW	BL	HG	WH	HH	HL	EL	CD
Breed x Age	37.55±2.08 ^c	49.31±0.85 ^b	56.50±1.28 ^b	57.70±1.65 ^b	55.48±2.29 ^b	15.45±0.37	15.64±0.63	14.11±0.32
Breed x Location	45.21±2.83 ^a	52.02±1.13 ^a	65.23±1.72 ^b	55.07±1.08 ^c	55.05±1.40	15.49±0.21	15.43±0.32	14.54±0.22
Breed x Sex	37.00±1.30 ^c	49.24±0.53 ^b	56.21±0.80 ^b	44.75±1.07 ^c	55.72±1.42 ^b	14.85±0.22	14.47±0.37	13.95±0.22
Location x Age	41.10±2.78 ^b	50.97±1.30 ^b	69.78±1.97 ^a	64.89±2.55 ^a	59.94±3.52 ^a	14.22±0.11	15.24±0.31	14.61±0.31
Location x sex	41.31±1.73 ^b	49.89±0.69 ^b	63.74±1.05 ^c	51.41±1.36 ^d	54.31±1.88 ^b	15.67±0.29	15.29±0.050	14.77±0.30
Sex x Age	40.92±1.30 ^b	50.02±0.53 ^b	63.30±0.79 ^c	57.03±1.03 ^b	55.18±1.42 ^b	15.62±0.22	15.44±0.37	14.54±0.22
P-Value	< 0.01	0.0027	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	0.1903	0.6381	0.1141

a,b,c,d,e means within the same Column and factors with difference superscript within the specific dentition group are significant different (P<0.01), BW= body weight, BL= body length, HG= hearth girth, WH = wither height, HH= hip height, HL= horn length , EL= ear length, CD= chest depth.

Table 8b: Two Ways Interaction Effect of Morphometric Attributes (cm) in Relation to Factors

Interaction/variables	CL	HC	NL	TL	FL	GL	GC
Breed x Age	29.67±0.27 ^b	32.44±0.67 ^a	18.23±0.29	10.26±0.23	15.89±0.21	12.66±0.28	18.10±0.28 ^c
Breed x Location	30.02±0.41 ^b	30.92±0.93 ^b	19.50±0.30	10.96±0.25	16.67±0.22	12.46±0.33	19.67±0.38 ^c
Breed x Sex	26.93±0.45 ^c	32.72±0.95 ^a	18.82±0.31	10.94±0.26	15.82±0.34	12.47±0.34	19.59±0.39 ^b
Location x Age	32.47±0.43 ^a	32.10±0.62 ^a	19.27±0.36	10.62±0.11	16.43±0.40	12.43±0.29	19.87±0.50 ^b
Location x sex	30.41±0.60 ^b	30.13±0.26 ^b	19.49±0.41	10.60±0.21	16.50±0.19	12.77±0.45	21.81±0.51 ^a
Sex x Age	30.02±0.45 ^b	30.92±0.95 ^b	19.50±0.31	10.92±0.26	16.06±0.24	12.46±0.34	19.66±0.38 ^b
P-Value	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	0.2202	0.3858	0.7745	0.0041

a,b,c,d,e means within the same Column and factors with difference superscript within the specific dentition group are significant different (P<0.01), CL= Canon length , HC= head circumferences , NL= neck length, TL= tail length, FL= face length, GL= gonadal length, GC= gonadal circumference.

Table 9a: Pearson Correlation Matrix of the Morphometric Traits

	BW	BL	HG	WH	HH	HL	EL	CD
BW	--	0.50**	0.91**	0.62**	0.51**	0.21**	0.45**	0.31**
BL	--	--	0.37**	0.34**	0.37**	0.03 ^{ns}	0.37**	0.25**
HG	--	--	--	0.59**	0.41**	0.28**	0.36**	0.26**
WH	--	--	--	--	0.74**	0.31**	0.38**	0.17**
HH	--	--	--	--	--	0.18**	0.48**	0.29**
HL	--	--	--	--	--	--	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.07 ^{ns}
EL	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	0.48**

ns= Non significant, **= highly significant (P<0.01), BW= body weight, BL= body length, HG= hearth girth, WH = wither height, HH= hip height, HL= horn length , EL= ear length, CD= chest depth

Table 9b: Pearson Correlation Matrix of the Morphometric Traits

	CL	HC	NL	GL	GC	TL	FL
CL	--	0.06 ^{ns}	0.36**	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.20*	0.24**	0.38**
HC	--	--	0.35**	-0.37**	-0.04 ^{ns}	-0.13 ^{ns}	-0.33**
NL	--	--	--	-0.06 ^{ns}	0.26**	0.26**	0.11 ^{ns}
GL	--	--	--	--	0.31**	0.19 ^{ns}	0.59**
GC	--	--	--	--	--	0.46**	0.18 ^{ns}
TL	--	--	--	--	--	--	0.18**

ns= Non significant, **= highly significant (P<0.01), *= significant (P<0.05) difference, CL= Canon length, HC= head circumferences , NL= neck length, TL= tail length, FL= face length, GL= gonadal length, GC= gonadal circumference

Table 9c: Pearson Correlation Matrix of the Morphometric Traits

	BW	BL	HG	WH	HH	HL	EL	CD
CL	0.43**	0.32**	0.45**	0.50**	0.33**	0.29**	0.40**	0.28**
HC	0.11 ^{ns}	0.20**	0.01 ^{ns}	0.38**	0.53**	0.05 ^{ns}	0.27**	-0.18**
NL	0.45**	0.24**	0.44**	0.63**	0.52**	0.28**	0.37**	0.21**
GL	0.19 ^{ns}	-0.20 ^{ns}	0.23*	-0.00 ^{ns}	-0.09 ^{ns}	0.21 ^{ns}	-0.13 ^{ns}	0.39**
GC	0.30**	-0.16 ^{ns}	0.36**	0.39**	0.09 ^{ns}	0.26**	-0.06 ^{ns}	0.05 ^{ns}
TL	0.29**	0.11 ^{ns}	0.32**	0.28**	0.00 ^{ns}	0.07 ^{ns}	0.27**	0.14 ^{ns}
FL	0.35**	0.11 ^{ns}	0.39**	0.12 ^{ns}	0.10 ^{ns}	0.24**	0.19**	0.58**

ns= Non significant, **= highly significant (P<0.01), *= significant (P<0.05) difference, BW= body weight, BL= body length, HG= hearth girth, WH = wither height, HH= hip height, HL= horn length , EL= ear length, CD= chest depth, CL= Canon length , HC= head circumferences , NL= neck length, TL= tail length, FL= face length, GL= gonadal length, GC= gonadal circumference.

Table 10 shows prediction of body weight from the morphometric traits measured in the indigenous breeds of goats. The coefficient of determination which showed that the independent variable explains the total variation body length, hearth girth and wither height were highly significant ($p < 0.01\%$) difference while Gonadal circumference was significant ($P < 0.05\%$) difference are best predictor of body weight.

Table 10: Prediction of Body Weight from Morphometric Traits of Goat Population Studied

Y	Intercept	Estimate	Parameter	Significance
	A	B	X	LOS
Body Weight	-81.11	0.92	BL	**
		1.08	HG	**
		0.02	WH	**
		0.02	HH	Ns
		-0.27	HL	Ns
		0.26	EL	Ns
		-0.02	CD	Ns
		-0.13	CL	Ns
		0.02	HC	Ns
		-0.04	NL	Ns
		0.10	GL	Ns
		0.24	GC	*
		0.16	TL	Ns
	0.14	FL	Ns	

ns= Non significant, **= highly significant ($P < 0.01$), *= significant ($P < 0.05$), LOS= least of significant, BW= body weight, BL= body length, HG= hearth girth, WH = wither height, HH= hip height, HL= horn length, EL= ear length, CD= chest depth, CL= Canon length, HC= head circumferences, NL= neck length, TL= tail length, FL= face length, GL= gonadal length, GC= gonadal circumference

4.1.2. Genomic Characterization of Indigenous Breed of Goat

Table 11 show the pairwise population matrix of Nei genetic similarity from 0.669-1.000. The highest similarity value of 1.000 was formed in all the population KNB, SHL, WAD and RSKT. The population had on the average similarity of 0.872 & 0.936 value of similarity is between RSKT and KNB, RSKT and SHL with 0.718 and the lowest similarity found between SHL and KNB with value of 0.669 respectively.

The unbiased genetic similarity values give the relatedness when all sources of error are removed from analysis.

Table 11: Pairwise Population Matrix of Nei Genetic Identity (Similarity)

Population	WAD	KNB	SHL	RSKT
WAD	-	-	-	-
KNB	0.872	-	-	-
SHL	0.870	0.669	-	-
RSKT	0.824	0.936	0.718	-

WAD= West African Dwarf, KNB= Kano Brown, SHL= Sahelian and RSKT= Red Sokoto

Table 12 gives the similarity value and confirmed the value in table 10 except that the value different strength

Table 12: Pairwise Population Matrix of Nei Unbiased Genetic Identity (Similarity)

Population	WAD	KNB	SHL	RSKT
WAD	-	-	-	-
KNB	0.938	-	-	-
SHL	0.934	0.713	-	-
RSKT	0.894	0.986	0.763	-

WAD= West African Dwarf, KNB= Kano Brown, SHL= Sahelian and RSKT= Red Sokoto

Table 13 show the pairwise population matrix of nei genetic distance. The nei genetic distance among all the population range from 0.066 to 0.402. The Table

shows that WAD population was genetically close to KNB population with value of 0.137 while they were much more genetically distanced from those of RSKT population with the value of 0.194 and SHL population with 0.139 value. KNB population had genetic closeness to KNB (0.137) to those of SHL population a (0.139). RSKT and KNB Shared genetically distanced (0.402) to those population RSKT and SHL (0.332) respectively.

The unbiased genetic distance value gives the genetic relatedness when all sources of error are removed from analysis.

Table 13: Pairwise Population Matrix of Nei Genetic Distance

Population	WAD	KNB	SHL	RSKT
WAD	-	-	-	-
KNB	0.137	-	-	-
SHL	0.139	0.066	-	-
RSKT	0.194	0.402	0.332	-

WAD= West African Dwarf, KNB= Kano Brown, SHL= Sahelian and RSKT= Red Sokoto

Table 14 gives the unbiased genetic distance value & confirmed the values in table 13 except that the values distance strength.

Table 14: Pairwise Population Matrix of Nei Unbiased Genetic Distance

Population	WAD	KNB	SHL	RSKT
WAD	-	-	-	-
KNB	0.064	-	-	-
SHL	0.069	0.014	-	-
RSKT	0.112	0.339	0.271	-

WAD= West African Dwarf, KNB= Kano Brown, SHL= Sahelian and RSKT= Red Sokoto

Table 15 the pairwise genetic differentiation value of population based on microsatellite loci (F_{st}) in this table were calculated for the four (4) population genetic differentiation between each of the populations. Population from different genetic

clusters appeared to be differentiated from each other corresponding well to the classification of the genetic cluster. The value obtained showed that there was free inbreeding among the population in different magnitude. The value range from -0.175 for complete panmixis, to 0.301 indicating that some of the population still share some amount of genetic diversity and the population were highly differentiated. The least genetically different population was between RSKT and SHL (-0.175), while highest between RSKT and WAD (0.301).

Table 15: Population Pairwise Based on Microsatellite Loci (F_{st}) (Gene Differentiation)

Population	WAD	KNB	SHL	RSKT
WAD	-	-	-	-
KNB	-	-	-	-
SHL	0.033	0.027	-	-
RSKT	0.301	0.293	-0.175	-

WAD= West African Dwarf, KNB= Kano Brown, SHL= Sahelian and RSKT= Red Sokoto

Table 16 shows the level of intra and inters population variation of F_{is} , F_{st} , and F_{it} . There are inbreeding coefficients: within population (F_{is}), between population (F_{st}) and overall population (F_{it}) for the five microsatellite loci investigated inbreeding within population (F_{is}) were positive & negative. The positive range from 0.04 to 0.39 while the negative range from -0.58 to -0.67 respectively. The inbreeding between population (F_{st}) range from 0.04 to 0.74. The inbreeding the overall population (F_{it}) range from negative to positive (-0.51 to 0.56). The estimate of gene flow range from 0.09 to 6.82 indicating effective gene flow in the population. The degree of genetic differentiation within population was very low, that of between populations was very high while overall showed a moderate degree of genetic differentiation. The percentage polymorphism was 100% on locus ILSTS005 while locus OARFCB484

and ILSTS001 were 80% and 60% on locus ILSTS005 and MAF70 respectively. This showed that locus ILSTS005 and MAF70 had lower genetic polymorphism loci in the population investigation.

Table 16: F-Statistics and F Estimate of Nm Overall Population for each Locus

Locus	H_t	Mean H_e	Mean H_o	F_{is}	F_{it}	F_{st}	Nm	% polymorphic loci
ILSTS087	0.46	0.12	0.20	-0.67	0.56	0.74	0.09	100
OARFCB4	0.45	0.38	0.23	0.39	0.49	0.16	1.31	80
ILSTS011	0.23	0.19	0.18	0.04	0.21	0.17	1.19	80
ILSTS005	0.50	0.48	0.75	-0.58	-0.51	0.04	5.57	60
MAF70	0.48	0.47	0.45	0.04	0.07	0.04	6.82	60
MEAN	-	-	-	-0.16	0.16	0.23	3.00	76
SE	-	-	-	0.20	0.19	0.13	1.34	9.57

SE= Standard Error, H_t = Total Expected Heterozygosity, H_e = Expected Heterozygosity, H_o = Observed Heterozygosity, NM= Estimate of Gene Flow and F_{is} , F_{it} & F_{st} = Inbreeding Coefficient

Table 17 show the number of alleles, number of effective alleles, Shannon information index, observed heterozygosity, expected heterozygosity and fixation index for each of the population studied locus by locus measuring the amount of genetic diversity among the population studied. Their grand means and standard error over loci are showed the highest genetic diversity occurred in OARFCB48 ($N_e=2.18$, $H_o=0.50$ & $H_e=0.54$) for WAD and ILSTS005 and MAF 70 ($N_e=2.00$, $H_o=1.00$ & $H_e=0.50$) for RSKT. The lowest genetic diversity was observed in ILSTS087 & ILSTS0011 ($N_e= 1.00$, $H_o= 0.00$ & $H_e= 0.00$) for KNB, SHL and RSKT.

The total number of sample size were 4.20 with a range of 1-4 across the loci, the mean number of alleles were 1.80 and detected across all population for the five microsatellite examined. Number of alleles per locus overall population range between 2-4 with grand mean of 1.80 for all alleles in the entire population. The numbers of effective allele were totaled as 1.60 while the total information index was 0.48. Total observed heterozygosity was 0.36 indicating that the markers were

sufficiently polymorphic to determine genetic diversity in the goat population studied. Expected & unbiased heterozygosity was 0.33 and 0.37 respectively. Mean H_o was higher than H_e indicating efficiency to heterozygosity of these loci. The mean fixation index for the population was -0.08 indicating that the population had more heterozygosity than expected in contrast to positive value that indicate fewer heterozygosity.

Table 18 shows the analysis of molecular variance of hierarchical gene diversity. The result indicated that 53% of the genetic variance was explained by among individual, whereas 44% was explained by within individual and 3% of the variance was explained by among population with estimate variability ranging from 0.057 to 0.827. The analysis of molecular variance indicated the majority of the variance were partitioned among individuals.

Table 17: Sample Size, Number Alleles, Number Effective Alleles, Information Index, Observed Heterozygosity, Expected and Unbiased Expected Heterozygosity and Fixation Index.

l	Locus	N	Na	Ne	I	Ho	He	UHe	F
WAD	ILSTS087	5	2.00	1.92	1.67	0.80	0.48	0.53	-0.67
	OARFCB48	6	3.00	2.18	0.89	0.50	0.54	0.59	0.08
	ILSTS011	5	2.00	1.47	0.50	0.40	0.32	0.36	-0.25
	ILSTS005	5	2.00	2.00	0.69	0.60	0.50	0.56	0.20
	MAF70	5	2.00	1.72	0.61	0.20	0.42	0.47	0.52
	Mean	5.20	2.20	1.86	0.67	0.50	0.45	0.50	-0.10
	SE	0.20	0.20	0.12	0.06	0.10	0.04	0.04	0.20
KNB	ILSTS087	3	1.00	1.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-
	OARFCB48	6	2.00	1.60	0.56	0.17	0.38	0.41	0.56
	ILSTS011	6	2.00	1.80	0.64	0.33	0.44	0.49	0.25
	ILSTS005	6	2.00	1.80	0.64	0.67	0.44	0.49	-0.50
	MAF70	5	2.00	2.00	0.69	0.60	0.50	0.57	-0.20
	Mean	5.20	1.80	1.64	0.51	0.35	0.35	0.39	0.03
	SE	0.58	0.20	0.17	0.13	0.13	0.09	0.10	0.21
SHL	ILSTS087	3	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-
	OARFCB48	4	2.00	1.28	0.38	0.25	0.22	0.25	-0.14
	ILSTS011	4	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.50	0.50	0.50	-
	ILSTS005	4	2.00	1.88	0.66	0.75	0.47	0.54	-0.60
	MAF70	3	2.00	1.80	0.64	0.00	0.44	0.53	1.50
	Mean	3.60	1.60	1.39	0.34	0.20	0.23	0.26	0.09
	SE	0.25	0.25	0.19	0.15	0.15	0.10	0.12	0.37
RSKT	ILSTS087	1	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-
	OARFCB48	4	2.00	1.60	0.56	0.00	0.38	0.43	1.00
	ILSTS011	3	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-
	ILSTS005	3	2.00	2.00	0.69	1.00	0.50	0.60	-1.00
	MAF70	3	2.00	2.00	0.69	1.00	0.50	0.60	-1.00
	Mean	2.80	1.60	1.52	0.39	0.40	0.28	0.33	-0.33
	SE	0.49	0.25	0.22	0.16	0.25	0.12	0.14	0.52
Total	Mean	4.20	1.80	1.60	0.48	0.36	0.33	0.37	-0.08
	SE	0.3	0.12	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.14

Pop= Population, N= Sample size, Na= No of Alleles, Ne= No of effective Alleles, I= Information Index, Ho= Observed Heterozygosity, He= Expected Heterozygosity, UHe= Unbiased Expected Heterozygosity, F= Fixation Index and SE= Standard Error.

Table 17: Analysis of Molecular Variance (AMOVA)

Source	DF	SS	MS	EST. VAR.	%
Among population	3	9.104	3.035	0.057	3
Among individual	23	46.917	2.346	0.827	53
Within individual	23	16.500	0.688	0.688	44
Total	49	72.521	-	1.574	100

DF= Degree of freedom, SS= Sum of square, MS= Means square, EST. VAR= Estimated variance and %= Percentage.

Fig. 1: Dendrogram

Dendrogram based on 5 microsatellite alleles generated from 49 goat individuals representing four populations. The scale bar under the tree represents one band difference refers to the population, followed 1 to 4 representing the population as follows: Breeds are abbreviated to as SHL= Sahelian, WAD =West African dwarf, KNB=Kano Brown and RSKT=Red Sokoto

4.2. DISCUSSION

4.2.1 Morphological Characterization of Indigenous Breeds of Goat

Variation in the morphological feature among the goat breeds may be as result of hereditary potential, geographical distribution, environmental condition and production system (Gizaw, Arendonk, Komen, Windig & Hanotte, 2007). Documentation of morphological characteristic of indigenous livestock breed is important to implement reliable selection strategies for breed (FAO, 2007). Therefore, here we attempt to describe the morphological features of four of indigenous goat breeds in Kano state. Our data showed significant morphological variation among these breeds in terms of sex, age and location, which can be utilized for breed improvement programmes.

The higher co-efficient of variation (CV) observed in the present study indicates variability in phenotypic traits of some indigenous goat breed. The result obtained in the current observation show that the CV for morphometric traits recorded were low (7.53%), moderate (12.74%) and high (19.54%) respectively. This agrees with the work of Gatew (2014) who reported value of 4.6 to 36.1% among Borena goat. Bedada *et al.* (2019) reported CV value of 5.66 to 17.67% in the same trait. According to Ijomanta (2012) who work on red Sokoto goat reported higher CV of 25.19%, 21.72%, & 11.60% for live body weight, body Lengths, hearth girth and wither height respectively.

Breed had significant effect ($P < 0.01$) on all the morphometric measurement except TL & GL with Kano Brown showing better performance. This is an indication that goat breed has influence on morphological characteristics in terms of body forms and structure as observed in the present study. This agrees with the finding of Guifen *et al.* (2014) who reported a significant variation in morphometric & carcass trait of

different genotypes of goats. Similarly, the work of Sanni *et al* (2018) on different breed of goats (Kalahari, Red Sokoto, Sahel & WAD) native to Africa also detected a significant variation on morphostructural traits and it has been suggested that wide variation observed between Sahel & WAD could lead to heterotic gain (Zahraddeen, Butswat & Mbap, 2008). Some author's (Gizaw *et al.*, 2007; Agaviezor *et al.*, 2012) attributed this variation to inherent genetic potential of each breed, geographical isolation and ecological variation.

Location had significant effect ($P < 0.01$) on all the morphometric traits measured except TL for all the locations. The result of this study revealed that Body weight was higher for Bebeji, Kumbotso, Kano Municipal than Wudil, Dala, Rimin Gado, Ungogo and Tofa respectively. This might be explained by different factors such as nutrition, shortage of grazing area in the site could be implicated, farming system depends on extensive grazing without supplementation, the incidences of disease, the size & productivity of the grazing land can be taken as the main factors affecting livestock productivity in the study locations. Similar to this finding difference in genetic makeup of the animal, availability of feed resources base (in terms of quality and quantity), availability of natural grazing feed & the management condition of animal (Cam, Olfaz & Soydan, 2010).

Sex is an important sources of variation for live body weight and linear body measurement at all age groups. In all the locations, sex had significant effect ($P < 0.01$) on body weight, BL, HG, WH, HH, CL, HC, NL, FL and GC while HL, EL, TL and GL were none significant. The male goat were having higher value than females the sex related difference might be partly a function of the sex differential hormonal effect on growth. In addition to that, the differential obtained in the morphological traits of the sex could be attributed to sexual dimorphism (Adam, Ma'aruf, Haruna &

Sani, 2021). They also suggested that male might have a large season of mass gain each year throughout their lives while female divert annual resource into reproduction, rather than body mass (Ma'aruf, Ibrahim, Umar, Shuaibu & Okoh, 2018).

All body measurement increase as age group increase for 2 to 4 pairs of permanent incisors. In this study body weight had significant difference ($P < 0.01$) in all the age (dentition) group and the same was true for all live body measurements. The body of goats at 4 pairs of permanent incisor was 42.54kg which is greater than 33.5kg, and 36.4kg as reported for indigenous goats in Horo Gudure Wollega (Ahmed, 2013). The linear body measurement increase as animal advance with age 2 to 4 pairs of permanent incisors. According to Yoseph (2007) age increases with increases in dentition class up to the four dentition and then after it starts to decline or remains as it is. The size and shape of the animal increase until the animal reaches its optimum growth point or maturity (Yoseph, 2007).

The interaction effects of sex and age significantly ($P > 0.05$) were not observed in the HL, EL, TL, and GL while BW, BL, HG, WH, HH, CL, HC, NL, FL, and GC were significant ($P < 0.01$) difference. This result agreed with Alefe (2014) who reported that the interaction of sex and age group was significant difference ($P < 0.05$) on all the body measurement. Higher body weight of male than that of females at all ages is attributed to aggressive behavior of male during feeding and sucking and male sex hormones which has an anabolic effects. In all ages' group and measurement, male goat performed greater than female goats. This finding was in agreement with short earned Somali goat and Hararghe highland goat where value for male goat than their female counterpart in all ages group and measurement (Grum, 2010; Mahilet, 2012). But in contrast with the report of Alade, Abdulkareem and Asheik (2008);

Sowande and Sobola (2009) and Okpeku *et al.* (2011a) were female had higher body weight and body measurement than the male counterpart.

The interaction effects of morphometric attributes of goat population in relation to factors was significant ($P < 0.01$) differences were observed on some morphometric traits except on HL, EL, CD, NL, TL, FL, and GL. This present finding agrees with Alefe (2014) who reported that the interaction between the factors showed a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) on all the linear body measurement. The morphometric traits measured with highest value found at HG at interaction between location and age (69.78 ± 1.97), this may be as a result of availability of feed for free browsing in the study location and increase in age of the animals.

The positive Pearson correlation for morphometric measurement shows that goat breed are able to survive as a living entity. The Pearson correlation analysis showed that body weight has positive and significant ($P < 0.01$) relationship with all the morphometric characteristics indicating that selection for body weight may yield a corresponding positive result in other morphometric characteristic. The relationship between the variable measured showed a direct proportional relationship (an increase in any one can lead to increase in body weight) while some had negative relationship. This could be used in the selection criteria for any breeding objectives in goat breeding in which emphasis could be given on those with positive and significant ($P < 0.01$) relationship against the variable with negative relationship. This result is similar to the report of Ogah, Musa and Yusuf (2013) for WAD goat breed, Adeyinka and Mohammed (2006) for Red Sokoto and Sahel goat breed. Okpeku *et al.* (2011), also reported similar result for WAD and Red Sokoto breeds. The relationship existing among linear body traits provide useful information on performance, productivity and Carcass characteristic of farm animal (Ngere, 2006) and have been

found useful in quantifying body size (Ibe & Ezekwe, 1994). According to Chineke (2000) the quantitative measurement for size and shape are necessary for estimating genetic parameters in animal breeding program.

The prediction of body weight from morphometric traits measured in indigenous goat breed was found to be 0.6749 as the co-efficient of determination which show that independent variable explain 67.47% of the total variation. Body length, hearth girth and wither height were significantly ($P < 0.01$) predicted body weight while Gonald circumference was significantly different ($P < 0.05$). The result also revealed that body weight has highest co-efficient determination followed by hearth girth while the least of determination was observed from wither height which differ with the finding of Dankoli, Umar, Ogah and Muhammed (2021). Further addition of addition of body measurement in predicting equation made substantial improvement of R^2 .

4.2.2. Genetic Variability and Similarity of the Goat Population Studied

These result provide important information for the future breed genetics improvement, management and conservation of Nigeria goat genetic resources.

The classification and characteristic of livestock species/types is necessary before desired morphology genetic materials can be preserved for future generation. Much genetic variability, the raw material for breeding improvement has been lost in developed country. There is no doubt that preserving genetic diversity, for either immediate or future use, is of great important.

Genetic similarity and relatedness

The result of the nei's genetic similarity showed the populations of goat in the studied locations were related at all the populations, indicating that there was a gene exchange between them (1.000). The populations with value ranging from 0.669 to

1.000 had some level of genetic similarity among them similar to the finding of Udeh (2015) who obtained the same result of genetic similarity for the study of genetic diversity of five population of the Nigeria Local breed of goats using RAPD makers.

Genetic distance

Genetic distance is a measure of genetic divergence between breed or between populations within a breed as indicated by Nei's genetic distance values, F_{st} values, mean fixation index and hierarchical clustering dendrogram. The result of this study showed that some of the populations were genetically close KNB & SHL (0.137 – 0.139) while some were farther apart SHL & RSKT (0.000 – 0.402) indicating that those that were close right have shared and some connections in terms of their locations or gene. Those that were farther apart right have some level of distinctiveness in term of their locations or other traits. This result agrees with finding of Udeh (2015) who obtained genetic distance result ranging from 0.0005 to 0.0507, Adebambo (2003) from the smaller drawn from several states across Nigeria and Okpeku *et al.*, (2011).

Population differentiation

The result obtained/recorded showed that the degree of genetic differentiation within populations was very low (60%), that of between the population were very high (100%) while the overall showed a moderate (80%) degree of genetic differentiation. This was an indication that the populations are not experiencing panmixis (free interbreeding) but they still share some amount of genetic diversity and the populations were somehow differentiated. The mean inbreeding coefficient between ($F_{st} = 0.23$) observed in this study was higher than the value obtained from Murital *et al.* (2015) on the genetic diversity & population structure of Nigeria indigenous goat using DNA microsatellite marker. The value of inbreeding coefficient

within ($F_{is} = -0.16$) in the most natural population are close to zero. The F_{is} value provides the non-random union gametes in population, which is the mating among individual in the population which is related more than average relationship. The higher the inbreeding coefficient (F_{is}) value, the more the degree of inbreeding. The negative value of inbreeding coefficient (F_{is}) point towards outbreeding and excess of heterozygosity in a population. For population mating at random, genes are equally related within or between individual & in this case, value of inbreeding coefficient is zero ($F_{is} = 0$). Therefore, the estimates of F_{is} that differ significantly indicate departures from random mating. Any avoidance of mating of negative will cause F_{is} to exceed 0 and to be negative more commonly, F_{is} is positive which could be interpreted as evidence of inbreeding (Weir, 1996). In this study F_{is} values were positive (0.04 to 0.39) and negative (-0.58 to -0.67, mean = -0.16) indicating the deviation from inbreeding and show an out bred population meaning that they are less related. These result agreed with the finding of Murital *et al.*, (2015).

Allelic variation

The five (5) loci assayed were polymorphic for all the population with each having at least four alleles per population. The range of alleles assumed per locus. The genetically heterogeneous sample were observed to maintain the different allele frequencies for a microsatellite locus. This could be because those samples were under the different allele frequencies or because of intensive exchange of migrants in the populations. Allele frequencies in heterogeneous population may be established as a result of random draft. This finding agreed with the reports of Riyadh, Muneeb, Mohammed, Osama and Mansour (2012) on the genetic diversity of Ardi goat based on microsatellite analysis.

Genetic diversity and variability

The genotype data obtained showed a good level of informativeness having a percentage polymorphism value of first loci (100%), 80% for loci second & third and 60% for loci fourth and fifth. The percentage of polymorphism value depends on the number of allele detected per locus and their frequencies. The heterozygosity percentage observed for all the alleles (76%) fall within the observed levels of heterozygosity in goat population. The observed average heterozygosity ($H_o=0.36 \pm 0.08$), the expected heterozygosity observed ($H_e=0.33 \pm 0.05$). This result was lower than the finding of Riyadh *et al.* (2012).

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 SUMMARY

These studies were carried out to examine the morphometric character among the breeds of goat, to determine the influence of location, breeds, age and sex on morphometric attributes of goats breeds, to evaluate any existing genetic variance within and among goat population in Kano State, to determine the genetic distance & similarity or relatedness of goat population and to determine relationship between the variable from the studied goat population for prediction. In order to achieve this objectives, laid down procedure for this studies were carried out. Body weight and 14 Morphometric measurement were taken & recorded from 374 goat population across the 8 locality of Kano State. 6 Blood samples were taken from each (4) breeds 3 per sex of goats using 23gauge sterile needle & syringes place on EDTA tubes later used for molecular and genetic characterization of the breeds of goats. The result of the first parts of this study showed a significant effect of location, breeds, age and sex on the morphometric characteristics. The result equally showed the most of the morphometric characteristics could be used for to classification of the breeds in their genus.

The blood samples were subjected to molecular laboratory analysis. DNA were extracted, gel was run and PCR was performed for the selected sample using five microsatellite markers (ILSTS087, OARPCB48, ILSTS011, ILSTS005 & MAF70) to determine the existing variation within and among the population as well as genetic distance and similarity of goats. The result of genetic studies showed that the population were heterogeneous with high heterozygosity percentage. It also showed some of the population had some level of genetic differences (variability)

while other were similar. The population had a high genetic differentiation among the individual but moderate differentiation within population the result indicated that population were outbreed meaning and relatives avoided mating in the population due to the positive and negative value of inbreeding coefficient within (F_{is}). There was an established magnitude of genetic divergence (76%) among the population as shown from the result obtained from the studied.

5.2 CONCLUSIONS

The importance of phenotypic or morphological characterization of indigenous goat's genetic resources cannot be over emphasized. The result showed the presence of wide morphological and phenotypic variations within and among the indigenous breeds of goat population in various studied locations of Kano state. Due to the existence of varied locations with their accompanying unique climate and vegetation, the goat population in the studied areas have also developed varied morphologically adaptable characteristics to be able to survive and reproduce in those environments. Among the unique traits are the BW, BL, HW, and HL. These rich adaptable morphological traits could be exploited for future goat breed improvement programme. In spite of the variety of qualitative traits observed, traits like white colour and presence of wattle (which are good for adaptation in the hot and humid environment and also have positive impact on performance) were at the brink of extinction due to their low frequency and incidence in the goat population studied.

The obtained result showed sex effect on linear body measurement was an indication of hormonal effect resulting in sexual dimorphism in the goat population in the studied areas. There were also effects of location on linear body measurement was an indication of influence of management and environment on the performance of the goat population in the studied area.

The linear body measurement reflects breeds characteristics and the management condition under which animal are kept. The study also revealed a relatively high genetic diversity which is required for population to be more adaptive with the management and environmental change, the studied population were not genetically pure but heterogeneous with varying degree of genetic similarity (0.669-1.000), genetic distance of 0.066-0.402 and genetic differentiation (-0.175-0.301). Since there was no inbreeding (-0.16) as shown in all the population none of the population exhibited genetic uniqueness revealed the efficiency of microsatellite marker in detecting the polymorphism among the breeds and established relationship among them. The genetic diversity of the goat population was high, as indicated by high mean number of alleles and expected heterozygosity recorded. The microsatellite marker used in this studied were quite informative for study the genetic diversity of goat thus could be included information of effective conservation strategy.

Lastly, the morphometric measurement could be used in breeding programmes as a measure of direct selection for goat breed with better body weight traits (46.17 ± 1.30) for Kano brown, (20.00 ± 9.13) for KNB X WAD, Red Sokoto (43.07 ± 2.72), SHL (41.85 ± 1.35) and 33.91 ± 1.40 for West African dwarf respectively.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

The following can be recommended from this study are as follows: -

- I. It is recommended that morphometric characteristics should be used to generate reliable information for goat discrimination due to their morphological differences.
- II. Morphological characteristics of goat populations were determined by genetic, environment and the interaction between and among them, therefore it is recommended that the environment should be well managed

interm of feeding and health conditions so as to enhance proper morphological development.

- III. Due to positive and significant relationship between body weight and others morphometric measurement, it is recommended that the selection or breeding index method should by employed for better goats population.
- IV. Measures to conserve uniqueness and distinctness of goat populations should be sought through genetic improvement; appropriate breeding policies and strategies should be developed and adopted to improved goat populations in Kano State.
- V. The genetic characterization revealed a wellbeing and conserved population due to their genetic similarity (0.669-1.000), distance (0.066-0.402) and differentiation (-0.175-0.301), thus there should be continuity in policy and decision making to retain and maintain the genetic resources for breeding purpose in Kano state.
- VI. Baseds on genetic distance, genetic differentiation and similarity, and high level of heterozygosity, it is better to employ all the loci as basis for selection through marker assisted selection (MAS) and indigenous breeding so as to ensure highest genetic gain.

Appendices

Appendix. I: Measuring the morphometric traits (a - d)

(a) Sahelian Goat

(b) West African Dwarf

(c) Red Sokoto Goat

(d) Kano Brown

Appendix II: Laboratory Practical on Molecular DNA Analysis (a – f)

(a) DNA Extraction

(b) Loading samples in PCR

machine

(c) Pouring of gel

(d) 2x master mix

(e) Primer

(f) Auto centrifuge

**Appendix III: Gel Image for Goat Population Showing the Bands of the Used
Microsatellite Markers (a-e)**

(a) Sample 1

(b) Sample 2 – 7

(c) Sample 8-13

(d) Samples 14 – 19

(e) Sample 20 - 24

Key: Samples 1-6= West Africa Dwarf, Samples 7-12= Kano Brown, Samples 13-18= Sahelian and Samples 19-24= Red Sokoto

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